

SEAMAN

Spatially resolved Ecosystem models and their Application to Marine Management

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D5.1 Manuscripts on the impact of an oil spill on the LTL groups, ichthyoplankton, and fish recruitment

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SEAMAN: Spatially resolved Ecosystem models and their Application to Marine Management

D5.1 Manuscripts on the impact of an oil spill on the LTL groups, ichthyoplankton, and fish recruitment and on the effects of mercury on fish recruitment.

Deliverable summary

In work package 5 “Pollution and climate stress on fish” pollution and different models of fish and fish recruitment were combined. The studies were focused on oil pollution and mercury. Different regions were investigated; Aegean Sea, North Sea, Norwegian Sea, and Baltic Sea. In the Aegean Sea anchovy is a very important species and the potential effect of both continuous oil spills from ship traffic and a potential accident from a drilling platform were investigated (1). In the North Sea and Norwegian Sea, the potential impact of oil spill from a ship-accident on early life stages of cod were investigated (2). Mercury is a potentially long-term pollutant. A coupled atmosphere-ocean-biogeochemical model was formulated, tested and provided modeled fields of mercury in the North and Baltic Sea region (3). The results from this model were used as input to a model to study the potential for bioaccumulation in macrobenthos and fish in the North Sea and Baltic Sea (4).

Key results for impact on oil spills on anchovy in the Aegean Sea:

- The mean oil concentrations of about 1 mg/l in the central Northern Aegean for the case of the illicit discharges.
- These concentrations might not be harmful to the adult fish (90 to 18000 mg/l) but is in the range of the lethal concentration for the larvae (0.1 - 100 mg/l).
- In the case of an accident in one of the oil drilling platforms located in the Prinos area, the simulated oil dispersion in the North Aegean Sea showed that there was a major impact in the areas neighbouring the platform position with oil concentrations from 20 to 3000 mg/l, having an impact mainly in the late larvae stages.

Key results for impact of oil spills from ship on cod eggs and larvae

- The oil-spill-IBM simulation used atmospheric and oceanic reanalysis products to compute the risk of oil spill at certain location along major ship routes will impact the early life stages of cod in different years.
- The simulations show that the locally an oil spill may in a certain location may in some years not impacting the cod eggs and larvae at all and while in other years entirely contaminating the spawning grounds.
- In certain locations, variations wind, currents and Stokes drift can explain the interannual variability in contamination.

Key results from the marine and atmospheric mercury cycle model:

- A regional chemistry transport model for the atmosphere was coupled to a Eulerian chemistry transport model for the regional ocean and used to investigate the air-sea exchange of mercury in the North and Baltic Sea.
- The model provided the first estimates for annual mercury emissions and their variability from both the North and Baltic Seas and is in good agreement with observations.
- The modeled average annual mercury emission into the atmosphere for the time from

1994 to 2008 is in the range of 6500 kg/a to 8100 kg/a for the Baltic Sea and 2400 to 3950 kg/a for the North Sea.

- The model indicates that there is a strong gradient in the air-sea flux from highly polluted coastal regions in the Belt and Arkona Sea, which dominate the total mercury evasion from the Baltic Sea.

Key results for impact of mercury on cod in the North Sea

- Most MeHg is accumulated in the central North Sea and along the outflows of major river systems in the Baltic. Little MeHg was accumulated in the Elbe river plume, likely due to the strong tidal mixing and frequent water mass exchange in the southern North Sea.
- The overall levels of bioaccumulations agree with published observations of mercury concentrations between 0.006 to 0.4 mg Hg per kg wet-weight in herring (planktivorous species) in the Norwegian Sea and North Sea with mercury concentration increasing with fish age.
- Including the bioaccumulation of pollutants into hydrodynamic and ecosystem models, shows that realistic values and patterns can be predicted. With further development and verification, these models can provide information on the spatial and temporal distribution of bioaccumulation to inform ecosystem and fisheries management.

Contributions:

1. Manuscript on the impact of an oil spill on the LTL groups, ichthyoplankton, and fish recruitment

Authors: Tsiaras, K., Krokos, G., Pollani, A., Petihakis, G., Kalaroni, S., Politikos, D., and G. Triantafyllou (Partner 6, HCMR, Greece)

2. Manuscript: Risk of oil contamination of fish eggs and larvae under different oceanic and weather conditions

Authors: Annette Samuelsen, Ute Daewel and Cecilie Wettre

3. Submitted manuscript: Impact of marine mercury cycling on coastal atmospheric mercury Concentrations in the North- and Baltic Sea region.

Authors: Bieser, Johannes and Schrum, Corinna

4. Report: A generalized approach to model bioaccumulation of Methylmercury in fish and Macrobenthos

Authors: Corinna Schrum, Sebastian Mentze, Johannes Bieser, Ute Daewel

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Manuscript on the impact of an oil spill on the LTL groups, ichthyoplankton, and fish recruitment

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List of abbreviations

1 Introduction

The Mediterranean is considered to be relatively more polluted by oil compared to any other sea, which actually data are available (UNEP, 1977; US-National-Academy-of-Sciences, 1975). Although up today there have also been no major oil spills, a large number of minor accidental or deliberate spills occur per annum linked to oil transport activities within the region. Pollution has been observed alongside tanker routes, particularly in the eastern Mediterranean Sea (Levy et al., 1981). Additionally, considerable quantities of oil are released from coastal urban and industrial areas (UNEP, 1977). Le Lourd (1977) estimated the amount of oil released straight into the Mediterranean, between 0.5 and 1 million tones per year, half being discharged from the coast and half from the open sea. This amount represents 1/5 of a given total marine oil inputs (around 4 million tones) released within a region that represents less than 1% of a given total world ocean surface.

Oil is composed 50-98% of hydrocarbons, which can include alkanes, cycloalkanes, and aromatic compounds. Of a given remaining compounds, sulfur is often present in significant amounts, while lipids and nitrogen based compounds can be found as well but in smaller amounts (Shaw, 1977). The total number of carbon atoms in each molecule inside the various fractions of oil determines, to the large extent, its fate after an oil spill. Petroleum discharged on the sea surface undergoes physical, and chemical, alteration. Rapid physical and chemical processes include spreading and movement with wind and currents, evaporation of one's volatile components, solution, emulsification (dispersion of small droplets into the water), sedimentation, and spray injection straight into the air and chemical oxidation. Concurrent with physical and chemical alterations are biological processes that operate most effectively when physical processes have already been initiated. Biological processes include degradation of given oil by microorganisms and uptake by larger organisms. The assorted physical and chemical processes alter continuously the composition in an oil spill (McAuliffe, 1977). Oils, composed of a lighter fraction, are more toxic as they simply disperse faster following the water currents, forming a thin film of about 0.1 mm on top. They are also the subjects of fast evaporation, contrastingly to the heavier fractions, which tend to form tar balls drifting with the currents until they are either cast ashore or biodegraded by microorganisms and sink into the ocean floor.

Observations on any number of oil spill accidents; show that the impact on the planktonic community is certainly not of a long-term nature. The water exchange and turbulence in offshore areas rapidly dilute the oil and exchange the affected communities. It seems probable that the time frame necessary for the recovery of one's plankton community from single spills is usually a question of weeks rather than months. Extensive and lasting damage was caused towards the littoral communities after the 'Tampico Maru', 'Florida', 'Arrow', 'Thesis', 'Exon Valdez', 'Amoco Cadiz' and 'Torey Canyon' oil spills. These accidents took place in bays and estuaries, in which the spilled oil was not diluted sufficiently.

The immediate effects of catastrophic oil spills can be obvious although their long-term consequences are often hard to quantify because the abundance of plants and animals in a locality fluctuates naturally from year to year while fish catches vary with fishing effort along with other reasons. Even 1 ug/l of oil dispersed in seawater can harm sensitive organisms. The toxicity of petrochemicals relies upon its water-soluble hydrocarbon composition (Carr and Reish, 1977). Bivalves may take up and concentrate hydrocarbons from the water, either from solution or adsorbed to suspended particles. Depuration rates are extremely slow, partly as a consequence of continual input of oil from the sediment. Although short-term exposures of bivalves to petroleum results in few deaths, their behavioral response may be of great importance to their survival (Taylor and Karinen, 1977). Fish is assumed to have the ability to avoid or leave oil-polluted areas unless behavioral patterns restrict them to a small territory. After an oil spill accident, the neighborhood fishery usually collapses either because fish departs from the area or die as a consequence of oil toxicity.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Model description

The oil-spill forecasting model developed for the POSEIDON system is based on the PARCEL model (Petihakis et al., 2001; Pollani et al., 2001) which is able to simulate not only the drift of the oil but also the chemical transformations under the specific environmental conditions. The oil slick is represented as "parcels" that have time dependent chemical and physical characteristics. The 3-D position of each parcel is calculated using advection and diffusion estimates while additional information such as wind and wave conditions and hydrological characteristics are requested for the simulation of the varying physicochemical

properties. The basic processes simulated by the oil-spill model are evaporation, emulsification, beaching, and sedimentation. The evaporation process (transfer of oil from the sea surface to the atmosphere) influences mainly the lighter fractions of the hydrocarbons and can result in 20–40% loss of oil in the first few hours. It is affected by the surface area and thickness of the spill, the vapor pressure, the wind speed and the temperature (Reed, 1992). Stiver and Mackay (1984); Stiver et al., (1989), have suggested the method used to characterize the evaporation of the oil. The emulsification process describes the mixing of water in the heavier fractions of the hydrocarbons and is affected by the wind and wave conditions as well as by temperature and spill characteristics (local thickness, the degree of weathering etc.). Riemsdijk van Eldik et al. (1986) has proposed the numerical approach of the emulsification process, which is used in the oil-spill model. The sedimentation process describes the trapping of oil particles that reach the sea bottom while the beaching process addresses the trapping of oil along the coast depending on the type of coastline (rocky cliff, tidal flats etc.). For beaching and sedimentation processes the model uses the formula of Gundlach (1987).

2.2 Oil spill information

Sea-based oil pollution, accidental or deliberate, has shown to correlate strongly with shipping traffic and offshore installations (Ferraro et al., 2008). The North Aegean sea, situated in the passage between two seas, is a major traffic route for all kinds of ships, including oil tankers that transfer oil to and from the Black Sea, but also commercial and passenger ships, especially during summer period due to the high touristic density of the Aegean Sea and the surrounding coastlines. Heavy traffic poses a significant risk of marine accidents. In figure 1 data from AIS (shipping density for the last 6 months period of 2014) reveal the main traffic routes in the North Aegean. Shipping density exhibits fluctuations between summer and winter but main traffic routes remain the same during both periods.

Furthermore, data from observed oil spills from satellites reveal that heavy traffic areas are also prominent sites for deliberate illegal oil discharges. In this latter case, the oil spill discharges follow a combination of heavy traffic routes and areas that do not belong to the neighboring countries territorial waters.

The Aegean Sea is also a place where offshore oil drilling platforms are operating while new ones are scheduled to operate in the near future. Currently, all platforms are located in the narrow strait between the Island of Thasos and the mainland of Greece. The oil spill hazard scenarios are created considering possible accidents in these platforms, a threat that has been highlighted especially after the BP's oil platform accident in the Gulf of Mexico.

Figure 1. Shipping Density in the North Aegean Sea (combined vessels positions for the last semester of 2013)

Figure 2. Oil spill density for the North Aegean Sea for the period 1999-2004 from [Ferraro et al., 2008]

3 Experiment design and Results

The approach to possible marine oil pollution was split in two different scenarios. Scenario A is an effort to account for permanent pollution by sporadic illicit discharges from ships. Scenario B concerns a hypothetical accident in one of the offshore oil drilling platforms located in Prinos area, between the continental shores of Northern Greece and Thasos Island. The methodology used for these two scenarios follows the work of Liubartseva et al. (2015), taking into considerations the special conditions of the area.

Figure 3. Areas included in the oil spill simulation scenarios. Areas marked brown correspond to the constant spill scenario A, while the red circle denotes the point of Prinos oil platform for the scenario B.

3.1 Scenario A

This scenario is an effort to simulated sporadic pollution due to illicit discharges that have been shown to take place in the whole Mediterranean Sea. As already mentioned, these spills are highly correlated with heavy traffic lines and areas outside neighboring countries territorial waters. Following the density concentration of observed spills in the North Aegean seas, three areas were selected (figure 3, areas marked in brown) as a representative for the simulations.

The oil spill scenario considers random oil release in these three areas both in space and time, with different total volumes released, respecting the concentration difference of oil spill detections in the North Aegean Sea (figure 3).

The oil spill model is forced by the hydrodynamic model is described in Tsiaras et al. (2012; Tsiaras et al. (2014). Model results were used to develop the climatology for the period (2000-2008)

Figure 4: Monthly climatology (2000-2008) of oil concentration (Kg/m²), simulated by the oil-spill model for a release of $\sim 115000 \text{ m}^3$ over a 10-day period from a diffuse source based on oil spill density observations for the period 1999-2004 (Ferraro et al., 2008)

The experiments were run for 5 years, for the period 2000-2004. The oil parcels representing the spills are tracked for 15 days, representative for the period that oil can have significant concentrations before being diluted in the sea environment. Concentrations of oil was computed every 4 hours, from which monthly mean maps were constructed.

We consider that oil concentration depends on the season selected and reveal areas where oil is moved or trapped by characteristic circulation features. In figure 4, we present the results for each month. Although concentration of oil is higher in the areas where it is initially released, transport towards coastal areas is important and shows characteristic seasonal patterns. Dispersion of oil follows dominant circulation features and the impact on

coastal areas is strongly related to the complicated mainland coastline structure and the distribution, shape and direction of the islands. In general circulation in the North Aegean favors eastern propagation during autumn and winter months, while western transport is more prominent during spring and summer periods. Especially during summer (months 7-8), southward winds increase the export of oil towards the southern Aegean, further reducing the impact on the Northern coasts, where in general oil transport is not favored by circulation.

The major impacts are found on the islands surrounding the central North Aegean. The area of Halkidiki peninsula is also impacted, but the rate is strongly varying seasonally. Some effects on the eastern coastal areas are also apparent, following the intensification of southward coastal currents that develop and intensify during early winter periods. Finally the western North Aegean is less affected, mainly due to the position and shape of Lesvos Island, which acts as a barrier, reducing the propagation in the coasts of Minor Asia. However, during autumn there is evidence of oil intrusion in the narrow straits between Lesvos and the continental coasts.

3.2 Scenario B

The second scenario aims to simulate the oil dispersion in the North Aegean Sea, in a case of an accident in one of the oil drilling platforms located in the Prinos area. The experiments follow the set up described in scenario A, with the difference that oil is continuously released in the Prinos area, at the current position of the oil drilling platforms. The spill is simulated every month for the period 2000-2004, in an effort to examine the different pathways that oil follows, depending on the seasonal circulation regime. Oil concentrations are monitored every 4 hours from which monthly mean maps are calculated.

Similar to the previous experiment, the results in figure 5 show significant seasonal variability and have strongly depended on mean current direction. The major impact, however, is in the areas neighboring the platform position. Due to the placement of the oil platform between the mainland and Thasos Island, dispersion of oil is confined in the strait and has the major impact on the local coasts, while high concentrations remain for long periods in the area. Depending on the seasonal variability of local circulation, oil is transported towards east or west, with similar extend as far as area coverage is important. Lower concentrations, however, are dispersed over a much larger area, covering most of the northern part of the basin, confined by the various islands neighboring the mainland. Western propagation is limited by the

Halkidiki peninsula, which acts as a barrier, but is also affected by all seasons, irrespective of the main currents direction. On the eastern parts, oil follows the main circulation patterns and is dispersed by the various cyclonic and anticyclonic circulation patterns that develop seasonally. Oil parcels that reach the area of the Dardanelle straits finally follow the BSW flow in the North Aegean Sea, with a general southeastward direction.

Figure 5: Monthly climatology (2000-2004) of oil concentration (Kg/m^2), simulated by the oil-spill model for a release of 100000 m^3 over a 10-day period from “PRINOS” point source.

3.3 Prinos 2003

In Figure 6, the simulated oil concentration and the calculated late larvae mortality for July 2003 are shown, assuming a release of 100000 m^3 over a 10-day period from “PRINOS” point source. It may be seen that the larval mortality induced by the effect of oil is very low, considering that late larval natural mortality is ~ 0.05 in the model. In Figure 7, the calculated egg and larval mortalities are shown for a 100 times higher oil concentration (10000000 m^3 release). Late larval mortality induced by the oil in this case shows some maximum values that are comparable to its natural mortality.

Figure 6: Oil concentration (Kg/m^2) in July 2003, simulated by the oil-spill model for a release of 100000 m^3 over a 10-day period from “PRINOS” point source and calculated late larvae mortality (day^{-1}) (right).

Figure 7: Calculated mortality (day^{-1}) for late larvae (top left), early larvae (top right) and eggs (bottom) in July 2003, based on the oil concentration simulated by the oil-spill model (see Fig. 3), for an oil release of 10000000 m^3 over a 10-day period from “PRINOS” point source.

In Figures 8-10, the mean simulated larval biomass and egg abundance for June, July and August are shown with/without an oil release (10000000 m^3) on the same periods. The effect of the oil release is generally small and it may be only noticed in the larvae distribution near the oil point source.

Figure 8: Mean simulated larvae biomass (left) and egg abundance (right) in June 2003, with (bottom) and without (top) an oil release (10000000 m³) in 1-15 June period.

Figure 9: Mean simulated larvae biomass (left) and egg abundance (right) in July 2003, with (bottom) and without (top) an oil release in 1-15 July.

Figure 10: Mean simulated larvae biomass (left) and egg abundance (right) in August 2003, with (bottom) and without (top) an oil release in 1-15 August.

Figure 11: Simulated anchovy adult/juvenile biomass and egg/early larvae/late larvae abundance over 2003-2004 period, without an oil release (red line) and different oil releases (100000 m^3 , 1000000 m^3 , 10000000 m^3) in 1-15 June.

It has been recognized that oil spills could also have an unfavorable effect on the health of larvae hatched from fish eggs. Immature stages are sometimes more vulnerable to oil

pollution. Thus, the LC50 for mature fish ranges from 90 to 18000 mg/l while for the larvae the range is significantly smaller (0.1 - 100 mg/l). Oil compounds can enter the trophic chain and accumulate in living organisms via a range of pathways (Teal, 1977). It has to be noted that zooplankton can take up various hydrocarbons from either the food or the water, which is subsequently excreted in the feces. Experiments have shown that a couple of days were just enough for zooplankton to discharge most hydrocarbons (Lee, 1977). Zooplankton is one of the main preys of pelagic fish and hydrocarbons implicitly are transferred to fish, which might affect it on a long-term time scale. However, the ecological model cannot describe these processes, since hydrocarbons are not included in the state variables of the model.

In our experiments simulated results show mean oil concentrations of about 1 mg/l in the central Northern Aegean for the case of the illicit discharges considering that oil is speeded from the surface to the 10m depth. These concentrations might not be harmful to the adult fish (90 to 18000 mg/l) but is in the range of the lethal concentration for the larvae (0.1 - 100 mg/l). In the second scenario, we simulate the oil dispersion in the North Aegean Sea, in the case of an accident in one of the oil drilling platforms located in the Prinos area. Model results demonstrate that the major impact is in the areas neighboring the platform position. Due to the placement of the oil platform between the mainland and Thasos Island, dispersion of oil is confined to the channel and has the major impact on the local coastal areas, while high concentrations remain for long periods in the area. Model results show oil concentrations from 20 to 3000 mg/l that has an impact mainly in the late larvae (figure7, figure 11).

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Title: Risk of oil contamination of fish eggs and larvae under different oceanic and weather conditions

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Abstract

Oil spills from ships happen occasionally and, depending on the location of the spill and the ocean and weather conditions, the effect on the environment can be quite variable. Here, an oil-spill model was applied to determine spread of oil from spills at different locations along ship lanes off the coast of southern Norway for each month in the 20-year period 1991-2011. This gives information on where the oil is most likely to spread in a certain month and how much this varies between years. These results were combined with results from an egg- and larvae drift model for Atlantic cod (*Gadus morhua*) to determine the risk of oil impacting the recruitment of cod. The amount of eggs and larvae that are exposed to oil contamination were connected to the corresponding environmental conditions. The highest risk of overlap between cod and oil is during March and April, and is associated to the maximum concentration of eggs and larvae. Furthermore a spill on the Norwegian west coast poses a greater risk because of the ship lanes proximity to the cod spawning grounds. Most locations shows large inter-annual variability in the spatial overlap between oil and fish eggs and larvae, but it is not always possible to find a strong relationship with the environmental forcing. In some locations, wind, currents and Stokes drift can explain this variability, counter-intuitively there is a negative correlation between the number of oil particles in the water and the overlap with eggs and larvae. Onshore transport poses a risk because oil and larvae gets concentrated towards the coast. The study is intended to demonstrate how results from oil-drift and biological models can be potentially combined to determine, based on the location of the spill, month and weather/ocean conditions, the risks of oil contamination to marine organisms and a similar method could be applied to other species or in other regions. Since the oil spills are hypothetical, we cannot say anything about the actual damage to a population.

1. Introduction

Marine oil spill can affect the ecosystem both through its physical influence on the organisms and through effect on the various chemicals in the oil. On the physical side organisms can get caught in the oil. Oil can also form a barrier to the surface, for some species of fish this can be damaging when they come to the surface to fill the swimming bladder (Sundby *et al.*, 2013). There are also several chemicals in the oil, for example PAHs and MAHs (aromatic hydrocarbons), these can increase mortality for eggs and larvae (Barron *et al.*, 2004; Neff *et al.*, 2000). Oil can stimulate the formation of marine snow (Passow *et al.*, 2012) that subsequently sinks to the ocean floor where it can impact the benthic fauna. Once buried the oil will remain longer since the biological remineralization of the oil slows down in anoxic conditions. The use of dispersants to increase the rate of remineralization have also received attention in terms of its potential effect on the ecosystem (Kleindienst *et al.*, 2015; Vikebø *et al.*, 2015).

The present study focuses on the seas outside southern Norway, where the currents are dominated by the Norwegian Coastal Current (NCC) that flows along the coast all the way from the Skagerrak to northern Norway. This current would primarily transport oil spills, eggs, and larvae parallel to the coast. On the west coast the NCC flows side by side with the Norwegian North Atlantic Current (NNAC), which is a more saline current also directed northwards. Frequent strong

winds of variable directions and high waves occur, particularly during winter, this will also contribute to the transport of oil. Both of the NCC and NNAC have frequent mesoscale eddies and thus it is hard to predict the local currents on short time scales. The tidal differences and thus the tidal currents are small (< 1.0 meter) in the southern parts of Norway, but become larger in northern Norway.

The Norwegian Sea/North Sea is busy with ship traffic both in connection to general cargo transport and to the oil production in the North Sea. The region is known for rough conditions in terms of strong winds and high seas during winter and in recent years the Norwegian Coast have experienced several large oil-spill incidents involving ships, for example the Server-accident in 2007 contaminated large parts of the west coast (Boitsov *et al.*, 2012).

The currents, winds and waves vary both between years and seasonally. Because all of these factors will influence the trajectories taken by both an oil spill, eggs and larva it is likely that the risk of an oil spill impacting fish larva will vary both seasonally and internally. The main objective of this study is to determine the seasonal and interannual variability of how much oil spills at different locations can impact cod eggs and larvae. Furthermore to determine which environmental forcing factor most influence this variability. Although the locations of the spills are guided by ship-traffic density maps, we operate with hypothetical oils spills. The actually mortality-effect of the oil is also highly uncertain, therefore we estimate only the amount of overlap between areas with oil and areas with eggs and larvae and do not quantify the effect in terms of mortality on the eggs and larvae.

The properties of the oil and eggs and larvae themselves will also influence the results. The properties of oil will determine, among others, how easily it can be mixed down in the water column, how fast it will evaporate. Fish eggs and larvae can have different positions in the water columns, some species have eggs that sink or stick to the bottom, while others float at intermediate depths. Cod have positively buoyant egg and they will therefore be located close to the surface and are vulnerable to oil-spills. As they enter the larvae stage and the larvae grow they increase their ability to position themselves vertically in the water column. The vertical position can both determine whether they come in contact with an oils spill and the subsequent drift trajectory (Vikebø *et al.*, 2007).

While atmospheric reanalysis products have existed for many years (e.g Dee *et al.*, 2011), only recently several oceanic reanalysis products have been developed (Balmaseda *et al.*, 2015; Sakov *et al.*, 2012). Assimilating observation of sea-surface temperature and height, sea ice, as well as ARGO profiles, these products provide more realistic estimates of the physical model fields compared to free runs (Lien *et al.*, 2016). In this study we use oceanic and atmospheric reanalysis products to force both the oil drift and larvae dispersal models. The results are used to compute potential impact of an oil spill at different locations on fish recruitment both from a climatological point of view and in different years of the simulation period (1991-2010). While the subject of impact of oil spills on fish larvae by combining oil-spill and larvae drift models have been the focus of several previous studies (Spaulding *et al.*, 1983; Vikebø *et al.*, 2014), the novelty in this study is the evaluation of climatological and interannual variability in the risk based on 20-years of simulation and an analysis. We have chose simulate heavy oil as this would normally be the discharge in case of a ship accident. Based on these simulations, potential overlaps for different months and from different spill sites are computed as an average for all the years and also in each individual year thereby quantifying the interannual variability in the risk.

2. Methods

2.1 The oil spill model

The oil drift model, OD3D, (Martinsen, 1994; Wettre *et al.*, 2001) is a Lagrangian model that takes into account 3-dimensional currents in order to handle oil spills released at depth as well as oil that has been mixed down by breaking waves. The model has a database containing several types of oils, ranging from light to heavy oils and from different drilling points in the North Sea. These oil types differ from each other with respect to chemical characteristics and how they are affected by various oil weathering processes such as evaporation, emulsification, and vertical dispersion. For these model runs we have chosen to use ‘heavy oil’ in the spill simulations. The model requires information about bathymetry, as well as geophysical input such as currents, temperature and salinity at multiple depths, wind velocity at 10 m, Stokes drift, significant wave height, and mean wave period. In order to assess the oil drift in a certain month, oil was released for two hours every day over the course of a month. The oil is released as a number of particles, each representing a certain fraction of the total volume of oil spilled. In total 20 particles are released every day, making about 600 over the course of the month. Each oil particle has a residence time of maximum 6 days, after which the particle is removed from the simulation. Particles will also be taken out of the simulation when they beach, evaporate or are permanently dispersed in the water column. The model time step is 15 minutes. The temporal resolution of the geophysical forcing data is daily for the ocean variables, 6-hourly for the atmosphere variables, and 3-hourly for the wave parameters.

2.2 The larvae-drift model

The larvae-drift model is structured as an Individual Based Model (IBM: Grimm and Railsback, 2005) that is coupled to the physical environment using a Lagrangian transport model. The particle drift was computed off-line from the ocean circulation model because we use an ocean reanalysis product as the physical forcing. The transport model is based on the offline version of ECOSMO-IBM previously used for brown shrimp in the North Sea (Daewel *et al.*, 2011b) and was modified to be applied to Atlantic cod in Norwegian waters. The variables required from the ocean circulation model are 3-dimensional current velocities, temperature, and vertical diffusivity coefficients. Daily averages of these variables are provided at discrete locations, while the internal time-step of the IBM is 30 minutes.

The sum of advective velocity \vec{V}_a and diffusive velocity \vec{V}_d determines the particle displacement at a given time and location:

$$\frac{d\vec{X}(t)}{dt} = \vec{V}_a(t, \vec{X}) + \vec{V}_d(t, \vec{X}). \quad (1)$$

The input from the physical model was linearly interpolated to the particles location. The vertical diffusion was assumed to be a random process. With the dispersion coefficient, calculated by the hydrodynamic model, the diffusive velocity was derived using a Monte-Carlo method. As Atlantic cod eggs are known to have a specific density (e.g. Jung *et al.*, 2012) an additional term needs to be added to the vertical particle allocation. As in Daewel *et al.* (2011b) the formulation based on solving the vertical component of the equation of motion, where gravity, Stokes friction and the buoyancy term that results from the density difference between eggs and their environment (Archimedes’ principle) are considered. This term is expressed as equation (2), and discretized in time (equation 3):

$$\frac{dw}{dt} = g \left(1 - \frac{\rho_{water}}{\rho_{egg}} \right) - 6\pi r \eta w \quad (2)$$

$$w_{t+1} = \frac{w_t + g \left(1 - \frac{\rho_{water}}{\rho_{egg}} \right) \Delta t}{1 + 6\pi r \eta \Delta t} \quad (3)$$

here w is the vertical movement and g is the gravitational constant. The density of water, ρ_{water} , comes directly from the physical ocean model while the density of the cod eggs, ρ_{egg} , were computed from the equation of state based on salinity values, at which the eggs are assumed to be neutral in the water column. The observations that we found closest to our area was off the coast of Helgeland in northern Norway, which indicate a salinity of 31.2 ± 0.7 (Jung *et al.*, 2012). Since we know that the ocean model is too saline in the NCC, the assumed salinity was increased to 33.5 ± 0.7 . The radius of the eggs, r , were set to 0.675 ± 0.025 mm. The molecular viscosity, η , was computed as a function of temperature, salinity and depth (Riley and Skirrow, 1975).

The IBM describes the egg and yolk-sac larvae stages of Atlantic cod using the temperature-dependence for development rates as described in Daewel (2011a). The equations for endogenous-feeding (egg and yolk-sac larvae) include temperature-dependent utilization of yolk reserves and concomitant somatic growth of larvae. The effects of temperature on the duration of the egg stage and yolk sac larval stage of Atlantic cod were taken from Geffen *et al.* (2006) and Jordaan and Kling (2003).

2.3 The model input

2.3.1. Ocean reanalysis and derived fields

As the oceanic input to the oil and larvae drift simulation in the Norwegian Sea the output from the 20-year TOPAZ reanalysis (Sakov *et al.*, 2012) has been used. This model system is based on the Hybrid Coordinate Ocean Model (HYCOM: Bleck, 2002). The model assimilates remotely sensed sea surface temperature, temperature and salinity profiles from ARGO floats and sea ice concentration. The atmospheric forcing is the ERA-Interim (Dee *et al.*, 2011) and data is assimilated using the Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF) (Evensen, 2009) with 100 ensemble members. The reanalysis fields provide daily information on currents, temperature and salinity. The larvae-drift model also requires information about vertical velocity and vertical diffusivity. Vertical diffusivity was not saved during the reanalysis and vertical velocity is not computed in HYCOM, therefore both of these were diagnosed from the available model fields. The vertical velocity was diagnosed by integrating the continuity equations downwards in isopycnal coordinated as described in the HYCOM documentation (https://hycom.org/attachments/067_vertical_vel.pdf) The vertical diffusivity was diagnosed using a Richardson number based model (Pacanowski and Philander, 1981). The parameters chosen for the estimation of the diffusivity $v_0=50.0$, $\alpha=5.0$, $n=2.0$, $v_b=1.0$, $k_b=0.1$. The temporal resolution of the ocean reanalysis output is 1 day and the spatial resolution is about 12 km on a curvilinear grid. The model fields were projected onto a $0.25^\circ \times 0.125^\circ$ regular lon-lat grid before they were used as input to both the oil-drift and the larvae-drift model.

2.3.2 Wave model data

The oil drift model needs the Stokes drift as well as the dominant wave height and period. For this purpose a global hindcast with WaveWatch3 with parameterizations described in (Ardhuin *et al.*,

2010) was used¹. The temporal resolution of the wave input is 3 hours and the spatial resolution is 0.5°.

2.3.3 Atmospheric forcing

The wind field at 10 meters from the ERA-Interim (Dee et al., 2011) is used as the atmospheric forcing, the same atmospheric fields were used to force the ocean reanalysis. The temporal resolution of the atmospheric fields is 80 km and the temporal resolution 6 hours.

2.3.4 Spill locations

The oil-spill model was run with oil-release at 49 different points (Figure 1), selected based on information about shipping routes in the Norwegian Sea.

Figure 1. The study area including ship tracks (green/blue), oil-spill release locations (black rings) and spawning grounds for cod (magenta patches in vicinity of the coast).

2.3.5 Choice of species and parameters in the larvae drift model

One of the most valuable commercial fishes in Norwegian waters is the cod and the cod eggs are buoyant and therefore more vulnerable to oil spill, we therefore chose cod to be the species that we model. The spawning of the cod is taken from maps of spawning field downloaded (downloaded

¹ The product is available for download at:
<ftp://ftp.ifremer.fr/ifremer/ww3/HINDCAST/GLOBAL05/>

from the map tool of the Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries <http://kart.fiskeridir.no/>). The start and end month of spawning from each of the spawning ground was provided together with the geographical information (Figure 2). This was also used as input to the model, the number of eggs released was modeled as a Gaussian curve based on the start and end month of spawning (Figure 2). The intensity of the spawning vary between spawning grounds, in addition spawning intensity may vary from year to year (Sundby and Nakken, 2008). Both of these variations in spawning has been neglected in this study since we did not have information regarding this.

Figure 2. Left and middle: location of the spawning grounds after the individual spawning grounds have been regridded onto the model grid. The start and end month of the spawning is indicated by the color. Right: the spawning intensity is modeled as a Gaussian curve and defined by the first and last day of the first and last month of spawning respectively.

2.4 The statistical risk computation

In each of the spill locations about 20 oil particles were released every day in each month (about 600 in total) for all of the 20 years, and the positions and states of these particles were saved in order to compute the dispersion of oil from that point. The probabilities were computed on a 0.1x0.1 degree grid. The model differentiates between the states of the oil, it includes ‘at the surface’, ‘submerged’, ‘aged’, ‘evaporated’, ‘dispersed’ and ‘stranded’ oil. Only ‘oil at the surface’, ‘submerged oil’ and oil’ is included in the probability and risk maps.

A range of probability was decided upon to correspond to different risks. ‘Low’: less than between 1 and 10%, ‘moderate’: between 10% and 30%, and ‘high’: more than 30% probability of the oil spill ending up in the particular region. The overlap between oil and eggs/larvae was computed by gridding the oil, eggs and larvae onto the same 0.1x0.1 degree grid. The indicator for contamination in this study is the number of eggs and larvae that are present in a grid cell that contains oil. Depth was also taken into account when computing the overlap, the egg or larvae must be in the same depth layer of the model as there is oil to be counted as contaminated. It was differentiated between the eggs and larvae that were inside a high- medium- or low-risk for oil exposure area, but in the figures following in the result section we show the numbers of eggs and larva in regions with any amount of oil.

2.5 Environmental variables

The extent of overlap was related to the environmental variables that were used as forcing for the two models. The atmospheric and oceanic variables considered are listed in Tabel 1. Monthly time series of these variables were computed for each spill location by calculating the mean condition over a 4°x2° box surrounding each spill location. The geographical extent (in km²) as well as the total number of particles were also computed for oil, larvae and eggs to determine if there was any connection between these properties and the overlap between oil and early life stages of cod.

Tables

Table 1. Environmental variables considered for the analysis.

Description	Source	Short name
Westward wind at 10 m	ERA-Interim	U wind
Northward wind at 10 m	ERA-Interim	V wind
Significant wave height	Wave watch 3	Wave h
Significant wave period	Wave watch 3	Wave p
Westward stokes drift	Wave watch 3	U stokes
Eastward stokes drift	Wave watch 3	V stokes
Westward surface ocean current	TOPAZ reanalysis	U curr
Northward surface ocean current	TOPAZ reanalysis	V curr
Sea surface temperature	TOPAZ reanalysis	SST
Sea surface salinity	TOPAZ reanalysis	SSS
Vertical diffusivity coefficient (derived)	TOPAZ reanalysis	K diff
Vertical velocity (derived)	TOPAZ reanalysis	W curr

3. Results

The largest concentrations of early life stage of cod occurs in March and April, hence we focus on the results for those two months, first presenting the environmental variables in these two months, then the general distributions and dispersion of egg, larvae. In sections 3.3 we present an analysis of which spill locations pose the greatest risk and finally analyze which environmental variables that cause the variability in the risk.

3.1 Environmental variables

The climatological conditions were computed from the full 20 years of model results. The environmental variables in March and April changes from typical winter conditions with strong winds and high waves to more spring conditions with weaker winds and moderate wave height (Figure 3). The dominant direction of the wind is south, southwest in both month, the direction of the Stokes drift is from the southwest in march and more from the west in April. The ocean currents are less variable between the two months (Figure 4), the most notable feature is the NCC going along the Norwegian coast and the strong currents along the coast between 62 and 63 N. The currents are slightly stronger in March than in April.

The environmental variables that we consider in relation to the overlap between oil and fish eggs and larvae are not independent. Therefore it is useful to understand the relationship between the different variables and the correlations between the variables described in Table 1 (Figure 5). Naturally there is a correlation between the wind speed and direction with both ocean currents and stokes drift as the wind is the primary driver of both of these. Wave height and wave period is also

strongly correlated. High temperature and salinity is related to westerly winds, but not to southerly winds.

Figure 4. Speed and direction of the climatological ocean currents in March and April

Figure 5. Cross-correlation between environmental variables for the period March-April. Only the correlations with $r^2 > 0.25$ have been included on the figure.

3.2 General distribution of egg, larvae and oil

In order to understand the results it is useful to understand the general temporal and spatial distribution of egg and larvae. Though there is some interannual variation in the distribution and amount of larvae the variability is generally small, also by model design since the spawning grounds, amounts, and timing of spawning is the same from year to year. Since the release of eggs is similar each year, the time series showing the number of eggs and larvae is also quite similar from year to year (Figure 6). A typical temperature in this area is 7°C, at this temperature the eggs will remain in the egg stage for about 13 days and in the yolk-sac larvae stage for about 8 days. Furthermore an experiment where the currents were the same each year, but temperature and salinity were allowed to vary revealed that nearly all the inter-annual variability in the time series is caused by variability in the ocean currents and does not come from variability in temperature or salinity. The general spatial distribution of both eggs and larvae, are very similar in both March and April (Figure 7). The distribution is primarily decided by the currents and the total number of eggs and larvae, which are both similar in the two months.

Figure 6. Time-series of the number of particles south of $65^{\circ}N$ in each of the 20 model years.

Figure 7. Climatological spatial distribution of eggs and larvae in March and April, the two months with the highest abundance. The color on indicates the daily average of particles present in each model grid cell in that month.

Figure 8. Climatological dispersion of oil in March and April from three different spill locations.

Oil being released from one location, rather than a distributed spawning ground and also being more influenced by variable surface winds shows much interannual variability in distribution. But in general the difference between March and April is that, for the spills along the west coast, in March the aerial spread is larger and the high oil concentrations more often come into close proximity of the coast (Figure 8). The stronger winds and Stokes drift in that month is responsible for this. The risk of overlap between oil and eggs and larvae are therefore larger in March than in April.

3.3 Risk of contamination from different spill locations

The different release points can show a large variability in the amount of spatial overlap with eggs and larvae (Figure 9). In general the spills on the Skagerrak have a very low probability for overlapping with fish eggs and larvae from cod, while the spill locations of the southwest coast of Norway have a very high probability of affecting the cod spawned in that area. Further north it is not surprisingly the spill locations closest to the coast and thus closest to the spawning ground that pose the highest risk. For all locations it is March that is the month with the highest risk of overlap, although the total number of larvae is actually largest in April. For eggs the highest risk is in March as well as the largest number of eggs.

Figure 9: Number of overlapping (defines as being in the same 0.1×0.1 degree grid cell) oil and egg particles (left) and oil and larvae particles (right). The lines from the map on the right to the figure indicate the locations of the different spill locations.

Normally it is March that has the largest overlap when we look at individual years, but in certain years April and even February or April can also have a large overlap. An individual example of the interannual variability in the risk of overlap between eggs and larvae and oil is shown in figure 10. From this figure it is clear that an oil spill in a certain location could pose a great or small risk to interact with fish and larvae depending on the conditions in that particular year. In particular when both the larvae and the oil is concentrated towards the coast, the resulting overlap will be large.

Figure 10. Example of overlap between oil and cod larvae in March in two years with very large (1994: left) and very small (2001: right) overlap between oil and larvae.

3.4. Physical factors determine the risk of overlap between oil and fish larvae.

To determining which physical drivers affect the overlap, the oil spill points along the west coast were clustered into 6 clusters of based on their location (Figure 11). The oil spill points in the Skagerrak were disregarded since there was anyway little overlap (Figure 9). Correlation between the environmental time series, as described in section 2.5 and the time series of overlap was computed (Figure 12). Only correlation values $r^2 > 0.25$ has been retained for the analysis. For ‘Cluster’ 1 and 2 we find that in both March and April southerly winds and stokes drift would bring oil into the larvae areas. When the ocean currents were to the east (in March) or slower than normal in the notherly direction (in April) this increased the overlap. Since oil is primarily at the surface and is directly influenced by wind and waves, the currets are probably more important for the positions of the larvae. The ocean currents would also be relatively more important in April when wind and waves are generally weaker and smaller, so the ocean current become relatively more important also for the oil drift. Cluster 3 shows a similar results to 1 and 2 in March, while in April we find a connection with easterly currents and wave height. Easterly current will tend to bring eggs, larvae and oil towards the coast where they are concentrated, not being able to escape, and this causes a large overlap, as with the example in Figure 10. For the remaining clusters we find very little relationship with the environmental variables, except with eastward ocean currents in March in cluster 6.

Figure 11. Geographical location for the six clusters of release points that were used to relate the overlap to the environmental variables.

Figure 12. Correlation ($r^2 > 0.25$) between the environmental variables and the overlap between oil spill and eggs and larvae in March (left) and April (right).

4. Summary

A model system was set up to investigate the impact oils spills from ships in different locations and times on the early life stages of cod was set up. The system consists of an oil spill and a larvae drift model that were forced by the same ocean currents taken from reanalysis. The oil drift model was additionally forced by atmospheric and wave fields also from reanalysis. The IBM describes only the egg and yolk-sac larvae stages of cod. The eggs are given a buoyancy, while the larvae are treated as neutrally buoyant with no own swimming ability and the development time of both is dependent on the ocean temperature. The model system was integrated over the 20-year period from 1991-2010.

The model results show that April and March are the months where the overlap occurs because of the large concentration of eggs and larvae at that time. Oil spills close to the coast along the west coast poses the largest risk to the spawning grounds. At the same time there is large interannual variability, depending on the condition in a certain year. A spill at one location could either not impact the egg and larvae at all or contaminate a large area with high concentration of eggs and larvae. It is the drift of the oil that primarily determine the variability in the overlap since the eggs and larvae follow the ocean currents that vary less from year to year than wind and waves.

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Elementa: Science of the Anthropocene

Impact of Marine Mercury Cycling on Coastal Atmospheric Mercury Concentrations in the North- and Baltic Sea region.

--Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>The cycling of mercury between ocean and atmosphere is an important part of the Hg cycle. Here we study the regional contribution of the air-sea-exchange in the North- and Baltic Sea region. We use a newly developed coupled regional chemistry transport modelling system to determine the air-sea flux. The system is based on the meteorological model COSMO-CLM, the ocean-ecosystem model ECOSMO, the atmospheric CTM CMAQ and a newly developed module for mercury partitioning and speciation in the ocean (MECOSMO). The model was evaluated using atmospheric observations of gaseous elemental mercury(GEM), surface concentrations of dissolved elemental mercury(DEM), and air-sea flux(ASF) calculations based on observations made on seven cruises in the Baltic Sea and three cruises in the North Sea performed between 1991 and 2006. The evaluation gave, that the model is in good agreement with observations: DEM(NMB=0.27,N=20), ASF(NMB=0.25,N=20), GEM(NMB=0.07, N=2359). Generally, the model was able to reproduce the seasonal cycle of DEM and ASF. However, several high peaks during summer could not be reproduced. For a few sub-regions area mean annual mercury evasion from the sea were available from the literature. The modelled mercury fluxes were comparable to these previous estimates. The modelled area averaged annual mercury evasion from the entire Baltic Sea should substantial variability, but no trend. The modelled mercury evasion ranged from 6500 to 8100 kg/a for the simulation period 1994-2007. For the North Sea the model calculates an annual mercury flux into the atmosphere between 2400 and 3950kg/a. Running CMAQ coupled with the ocean model lead to better agreement with GEM observations at five EMEP stations. Directly at the coast GEM concentrations could be increased by up to 10% on annual average and observed peaks could be reproduced much better. At stations 100km away the impact was still observable but reduced to 2-5% on the annual scale.</p>
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Cover Letter

Dear Editor,

for the special issue “*Monitoring, Measuring and Modeling Atmospheric Mercury and Air-Surface Exchange – Are we making progress?*” we submit a paper on the air-sea exchange of mercury in the North- and Baltic Sea region. We think that this paper would fit both into the Atmosphere and Ocean part of ELEMENTA.

In the paper we present first results from our newly developed atmosphere coupled oceanic chemistry transport model (MECOSMO). With this model we want to set new standards concerning the regional high resolution modelling of mercury cycling in the environment.

We perform an evaluation of the model capability to reproduce observed concentrations of dissolved gaseous mercury in the surface ocean and the air-sea exchange. Moreover, we evaluate the impact of mercury evasion from the North- and Baltic Sea on regional atmospheric transport. The model compares very favorably to observations in the ocean. Furthermore, the feedback to the atmospheric chemistry transport model reduced the bias in atmospheric mercury concentrations in the model region.

With help of the model we are able to investigate the spatial and temporal variability of the mercury exchange between atmosphere and ocean. Before, this could only be estimated from a limited amount of in situ samples. We hope, that based on the model results future measurement campaigns on the North- and Baltic Sea can identify times and regions of high interest for further observations.

Yours sincerely,
Dr. Johannes Bieser

Impact of Marine Mercury Cycling on Coastal Atmospheric Mercury Concentrations in the North- and Baltic Sea region.

Modelling Mercury Cycling in the North- and Baltic Sea region.

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Abstract

The cycling of mercury between ocean and atmosphere is an important part of the Hg cycle. Here we study the regional contribution of the air-sea exchange in the North- and Baltic Sea region. We use a newly developed coupled regional chemistry transport modeling (CTM) system to determine the flux between atmosphere and ocean. The system is based on the meteorological model COSMO-CLM, the ocean-ecosystem model ECOSMO, the atmospheric CTM CMAQ and a newly developed module for mercury partitioning and speciation in the ocean (MECOSMO). The model was evaluated using atmospheric observations of gaseous elemental mercury (GEM), surface concentrations of dissolved elemental mercury (DEM), and air-sea flux (ASF) calculations based on observations made on seven cruises in the western and central Baltic Sea and three cruises in the North Sea performed between 1991 and 2006. The evaluation gave, that the model is in good agreement with observations: DEM (Normalized Mean Bias NMB=0.27 N=20), ASF (NMB=0.25, N=20), GEM (NMB=0.07, N=2359). Generally, the model was able to reproduce the seasonal cycle of DEM and ASF. However, several high peaks during summer could not be reproduced. For a few sub-regions area mean annual mercury evasion from the sea were available from the literature. The modelled mercury fluxes were comparable to these previous estimates. The modelled area averaged annual mercury evasion from the entire Baltic Sea should substantial variability, but no trend. The modelled mercury evasion ranged from 6500 to 8100 kg/a for the simulation period 1994-2007.. For the North Sea the model calculates an annual mercury flux into the atmosphere between 2400 and 3950 kg/a. The mercury flux from the ocean had substantial impacts on coastal atmospheric mercury concentrations.

Running CMAQ coupled with the ocean model lead to better agreement with GEM observations at five EMEP stations. Directly at the coast GEM concentrations could be increased by up to 10% on annual average and observed peaks could be reproduced much better. At stations 100km away the impact was still observable but reduced to 2-5% on the annual scale.

1. Introduction

Mercury is a toxic substance that poses a severe risk to human life and ecosystems. Because of its global nature, monitoring and reduction of mercury pollution has been a focus of several international conventions, such as the UN-ECE Convention on Long-Range Transport of Atmospheric Pollution (LRTAP) (ECE, 2010), the UNEP global mercury partnership (UNEP, 2013a), and the Minamata Convention on mercury (UNEP, 2013b).

The majority of mercury on earth is stored in deep mineral reservoirs (3×10^8 Gg). The second largest reservoir of mercury is the ocean with (~350 Gg) (UNEP 2013c). Historically, ocean, atmosphere, and biosphere were in a quasi steady state and the only source for additional mercury was volcanic activity, which is estimated to an average of 90 Mg of mercury emissions per annum (Pirrone et al., 2010). Because of mining activities and the extraction and burning of fossil fuels, mercury emissions into the atmosphere have increased dramatically over the past century (Horowitz et al., 2014). Amos et al. (2013) estimated that, compared to preindustrial times, the mercury burden has increased by a factor of 7.5 in the atmosphere and a factor of 5.5 in the surface ocean. In 2008, the estimated annual anthropogenic emissions of mercury from deep mineral reservoirs were 2000 Mg while emissions from the ocean were estimated in the range of 2500 to 4000 Mg. This shows, that the ocean is a major source for atmospheric mercury, even larger than the anthropogenic emissions. With the implementation of the Minamata Convention, future anthropogenic mercury emissions are expected to decline compared to today (Pacyna et al., 2006a). This will probably have a strong impact on the air-sea exchange. With decreasing atmospheric Hg concentrations, legacy emissions driven by past deposition into the ocean might increase and lead to an even stronger influence of the ocean on the global mercury cycle.

In the environment, mercury is constantly exchanged between ocean, atmosphere, lithosphere, and biosphere. Therefore, in order to understand the global fate of mercury, it is important to take into account all environmental compartments. By means of Monte Carlo simulations, Qureshi et al. (2011) found that the chemical reactions in the surface ocean and air-sea

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3 exchange are two of the largest sources of uncertainty in global mercury models. This fact alone, leads to the ocean being a
4 compartment of high interest for model studies in order to better understand the global cycle of mercury and its transport
5 pathways.

6 Here we aim to study the role of the ocean and the atmosphere-ocean interactions in the regional system of North and Baltic
7 Sea. For this study we coupled the eulerian regional atmospheric chemistry transport model (CTM) CMAQ with an ocean
8 coupled hydrodynamic biogeochemical model and expand this with a model for marine mercury cycling, resolving
9 transport, sedimentation and resuspension, partitioning, and chemical speciation of mercury to determine the mercury flux
10 between the two compartments in the North and Baltic Sea region. Here, we investigate the capability of the CTM to
11 reproduce elemental mercury concentrations in the atmosphere and the ocean and finally the air-sea flux itself. The mercury
12 flux from the Baltic has been estimated in the past based on a limited amount of observations. We compare modeled air-sea
13 fluxes and their spatial and temporal variability with observations and investigate the influence of the North and Baltic Sea
14 on regional atmospheric mercury transport.

16 2. Model description and set-up

18 2.1 Atmospheric modeling

19 Model description

20
21 To determine the mercury concentration in and the deposition from the atmosphere we used the chemistry transport model
22 (CTM) CMAQ (Community Model for Air Quality). The CMAQ model system was developed by the U.S. EPA and is
23 currently one of the most used CTMs worldwide (Byun & Ching, 1999; Byun & Schere, 2006). Here, we used CMAQ
24 version 5.0.1 with the carbon bond chemistry mechanism including updated toluene chemistry, improved chlorine reactions
25 *cb05tucl* (Tanaka et al., 2003; Sawar et al., 2007), and the multi pollutant aerosol module *aero6* (Yarwood et al., 2005;
26 Whitten et. al., 2010). The mercury chemistry in CMAQ is based on the implementation of Bullock and Brehme (2002) but
27 was updated based on observations and model inter-comparisons in the course of the EU FP7 project GMOS (Global
28 Mercury Observation System) (Bieser et al., 2015) (Eq. 1-1 to 1-5). CMAQ includes three mercury species in the
29 atmosphere: Gaseous Elemental Mercury (GEM), Gaseous Oxidized Mercury (GOM), and Particle Bound Mercury (PBM).
30 To determine the exchange of mercury between the atmosphere and other environmental compartments we utilized a bi-
31 directional flux implementation by Bash (2010). For the default CMAQ runs the dry deposition velocity of mercury is set to
32 zero above water bodies and the net deposition is calculated using a fixed concentration for mercury in the surface ocean
33 (Bash, 2010). In a second step we re-run CMAQ for the years 2000 and 2005 using the air-sea exchange calculated by the
34 ocean-ecosystem-chemistry model instead for the North- and Baltic Sea.

45 Atmospheric emissions data and regional meteorology

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47 Emission data for primary pollutants and precursors of ozone and secondary particulate matter were created with the
48 SMOKE-for-Europe emission model (Bieser et al., 2011a) which is based on the US-EPA emission model SMOKE
49 (Houyoux et al., 2000; UNC, 2005). Biogenic emissions and NO emissions from soils were created with the BEIS3.14
50 biogenic bottom-up emission model (Pierce et. al., 2002; Vukovich et. al. 2002; Schwede et al., 2005). Additionally, we
51 used the AMAP emission inventories for the years 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, and 2010 as source for gridded annual mercury
52 emissions (Pacyna et al., 2003; Pacyna et al., 2006b, Wilson et al., 2010). The SMOKE-EU model was used to temporally
53 disaggregate these emissions to create the hourly fields needed as CMAQ input (Bieser et al., 2011a). The speciation
54 between the three mercury species was based on observations by Weigelt et al. (in prep.) and the vertical distribution was
55 based on plume rise profiles by Bieser et al. (2011b). Finally, boundary conditions for the regional domain are taken from
56 monthly means of the TM5 global CTM (Huijnen et al., 2010) and were provided by the Dutch Royal Meteorological
57 Institute (KNMI). For the mercury species we used boundary fields from the global CTM GLEMOS (Travnikov and Ilyin,
58 2009).

59 All physical atmospheric parameters were taken from regional atmospheric simulations with the COSMO-CLM mesoscale
60 meteorological model (version 4.8) for the years 1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, and 2010 (Geyer, 2014) using NCEP forcing data
61 (Kalnay et al., 1996). COSMO-CLM is the climate version of the regional scale meteorological community model COSMO
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(Rockel et al., 2008), originally developed by Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD) (Steppeler et al., 2003; Schaettler et al. 2008). It has been run on a 0.22° x 0.22° grid using 40 vertical layers up to 20 hPa for entire Europe. COSMO-CLM uses the TERRA-ML land surface model (Schrodin and Heise, 2001), a TKE closure scheme for the planetary boundary layer (Doms, 2011; Doms et al., 2011), cloud microphysics after Seifert and Beheng (2001,2006), the Tiedtke scheme (Tiedtke, 1989) for cumulus clouds and a long wave radiation scheme following Ritter and Geleyn (1992). The meteorological fields were afterwards processed to match the CMAQ grid. CMAQ uses the information that is provided by the meteorological input fields to calculate transport, transformation and loss of all gas phase and particulate species. The impact of the meteorological fields on the output of the chemistry transport model was investigated in detail in the articles by Matthias et al. (2009) and Bieser et al. (2011a).

Model setup

The atmospheric model domain covers the entire European land mass, including north Africa and western Russia with a resolution of 72x72km and 30 vertical layers (see Fig. 2a). CMAQ is initialized by a mean concentration field and a spin up time of 14 days is used. Due to computational limitations it was not possible to create a continuous simulation and CMAQ was instead only run for every fifth year (1990, 1995, 2000, 2005, 2010).

2.2 Ocean modeling

Model description

Calculations of mercury cycling in the ocean are based on the ocean-ecosystem model ECOSMO (Schrum et al., 2006; Daewel & Schrum, 2013). ECOSMO is a regional 3-d Eulerian model that considers hydrodynamics, sea ice and biogeochemical cycling including phyto- and zooplankton production. The ocean hydrodynamics are simulated considering time dependent surface elevation and sea ice dynamics. The hydrodynamic model is a non-linear hydrostatic z-level model, which is using semi-implicit, energy and enstrophy conserving numerical methods. Scalar properties are advected using a shape-preserving total variation diminishing numerical scheme. The hydrodynamic model is in detail described in Schrum and Backhaus (1999) and recent numerical updates were described by Barthel et al. (2012). The ocean biogeochemical cycling and plankton production is resolved through simulation of 3 limiting macro-nutrient cycles, the nitrogen-, the silicon and the phosphorus cycle and oxygen. The model resolves three plankton groups, diatoms, flagellates and cyanobacteria, and two zooplankton groups. The organic matter cycling is furthermore resolved by dissolved and particulate matter groups and a simple organic surface sediment pool. A detailed model description of the biogeochemical cycling is given by Daewel and Schrum (2013).

To implement mercury chemistry in the ECOSMO framework we introduced the species elemental mercury and oxidized mercury into the model (Fig. 1). While elemental mercury is always treated as dissolved (DEM) in the aqueous phase, oxidized mercury is either dissolved (DOM) or associated to particles (PBM). Moreover, for particulate bound mercury we distinguish between three kinds of particles: phytoplankton (BPC), zooplankton (BZC), and inanimate particulate organic carbon (POC). Here we assume that only mercury bound to POC has a sinking velocity (10 m/s) and can accumulate in the sediment. For the dissolved-particle partitioning we use a partitioning approach following Brigham et al. (2009), assuming an instantaneous equilibrium at each time step. The partitioning coefficient K_d varies between 3×10^4 and 7×10^5 [l/kg] depending on the amount of dissolved organic matter OM_{dis} , which is estimated based on dissolved organic carbon (DOC) in the aqueous phase (Eq. 2-1 and 2-2).

$$K_d = 0.22865 * \exp(0.7505 * OM_{dis}) \quad (2-1)$$

$$PBM = K_d * OM_{part} * (DOM + PBM) * 1.0E6 \quad (2-2)$$

OM_{dis}	dissolved organic matter	[mg/l]
OM_{part}	particulate organic matter	[mg/l]
K_d	partitioning coefficient	[l/kg]
PBM	particulate bound mercury	[ng/l]
DOM	dissolved oxidized mercury	[ng/l]

Depending on the salinity, which varies between 1 PSU and 35 PSU in our model domain, up to 40% of the dissolved oxidized mercury (DOM) is considered to be bound in chlorine complexes and is not available for reduction (Mason et al., 1996). Thus, compared to the North Sea, there is a higher reduction potential of DOM in the Baltic Sea and near large estuaries where the salinity is much lower than 35PSU.

Inorganic chemical reactions considered are dark- and photo-oxidation of DEM as well as photolysis and biologically induced reduction of the DOM fraction not bound as chlorine complexes (Table 1). Reaction rates for inorganic mercury species are based on Soerensen et al. (2006; 2010) and Qureshi et al. (2010). In the model, all reactions are implemented as

pseudo-1st order reactions (Eq. 3-1).

$$C_t = C_0 * \exp(-a*k*t) \quad (3-1)$$

k	reaction rate	[see Tabel 1 for unit]
a	constant depending on reaction rate (e.g. Dissolved organic matter [mg/l])	
t	time	[s]
C _t	Concentration at time t	[ng/l]
C ₀	Initial concentration	[ng/l]

Moreover, it is important to consider methylation processes in the ocean, since MeHg forms a sink for DOM. Especially during the warm seasons, a significant fraction of the total aqueous mercury can be in organic form and the amount of DEM is indirectly influenced by the amount of methylated mercury. Here, we consider methylation and de-methylation of mercury in the model. The exact mechanics of mercury methylation are still not completely understood and published reaction rates show a very high variability (Sonke et al., 2013). For this study we estimated an average value for total methylation, dark de-methylation, and photo induced de-methylation rates (Heyes et al., 2006, Monperrus et al., 2007, Ranchou-Peyruse et al., 2009).

All non-photolytic reactions can also take place in the sediment. A simple 2-layer sediment compartment was implemented following the approach chosen for the ECOSMO biogeochemical model with the upper layer exchanging dissolved mercury from pore water with the water column above. In cases of high friction velocities (> 0.01 m/s) the particulate mercury in the first sediment layer can be re-suspended. The second sediment layer represents a permanent sink for mercury based on a fixed burial rate from the top sediment layer of (0.00001 d⁻¹).

Finally, the potential air-sea exchange of elemental mercury is calculated using the temperature dependent Henry constant (Eq. 4-1) for mercury from Andersson et al. (2008). The velocity of the exchange between the two compartments is dominated by the mass transfer coefficient in the aqueous phase. We calculated this coefficient using a parameterization for wind speed dependency from Nightingale et al. (2000) and included a temperature correction for the diffusivity of mercury according to Kuss et al. (2014) (Eq. 4-2). A detailed description of the method can be found in Qureshi et al. (2011). Sea ice is seasonally important in the Baltic Sea, in severe winters it might extend over almost the entire area. In case of sea ice presence, the air-sea exchange is limited to the open water fraction of a gride cell (Eq. 4-3). Mercury exchange between atmosphere and sea ice as well as ocean an sea ice is currently neglected.

$$H = \exp[-2404.3 / (T + 6.915)] \quad (4-1)$$

$$kw = (0.0025 * U10^2) * (0.0315 * (T - 273.15) + 0.784) \quad (4-2)$$

$$F_{wa} = (1 - F_{ice}) * kw * (C_{aq} - C_{air} / H) \quad (4-3)$$

T	temperature	[K]
H	Henry constant for mercury	[dimensionless]
kw	mass transfer coefficient	[m/h]
U10	wind speed at 10m	[m/s]
C _{aq}	mercury concentration in water	[ng/m ³]
C _{air}	mercury concentration in air	[ng/m ³]
F _{ice}	fraction of ice coverage	[dimensionless]
F _{wa}	flux water to air	[ng/m ² h]

Mercury riverine loads and emission data

Mercury sources to the ocean-sediment system are mainly from riverine loads and from atmospheric deposition. Atmospheric mercury deposition was taken from CMAQ. The river loads were implemented as annual and, where possible as monthly average values for the year 2004 based on national reported waterborne loads to the Baltic Sea (as reported by HELCOM¹; HELCOM, 2007) and to the North Sea (as reported by OSPAR² and retrieved for the Norwegian National Pollution Assessment for the North Sea waters (Green et al., 2011). Finally, initial sediment concentrations for the deep basins in the North Sea (Kersten et al., 1988; Leermakers et al, 2001) and Baltic Sea (Borg and Jonsson, 1995; Pempkowiak et al., 1998; Beldowski and Pempkowiak, 2003) were implemented based on observations.

1 Helsinki Commission, Baltic Sea Marine Environment Protection Commission

2 Oslo and Paris Commission, Protecting and conserving the North-East Atlantic and its resources

Model setup

The ocean model ECOSMO is setup on a model domain covering the entire Baltic Sea and the North Sea (Fig. 2b). Open boundaries are in the English Channel and at 63° North, where the North Sea is connected to the Atlantic. The resolution of the model is about 10x10km² (spherical grid) with a top layer depth of 5m and up to 20 layers to resolve the vertical direction up to a max. water depth of 630m. The ocean mercury model was run for the time span 1993 to 2008. Hydrodynamics and ocean biogeochemistry data were taken from an earlier published and in detail validated multi-decadal ocean model hindcast (Daewel & Schrum, 2013). Ocean mercury concentrations are transported in the water column using daily mean currents, sea level and turbulence from the existing long-term simulation. The Eulerian advection-turbulent diffusion algorithm used for the mercury transport in the ocean is the same as in the ECOSMO model (Daewel & Schrum, 2013; Barthel et al., 2012). Partitioning and chemical speciation of mercury in the ocean are calculated using the daily mean temperature, salinity, plankton-, organic matter- and sediment carbon contents from the long-term simulation. Light conditions used to calculate photolytic reactions are calculated in a similar way as in the ECOSMO model (Daewel & Schrum, 2013).

We created an initial concentration field for all mercury species in order to start the model in a quasi realistic state. For this, we interpolated 1452 observations of mercury in the North and Baltic Sea between 1980 and 2010 using a bi-linear interpolation approach. The observational mercury data were retrieved from the ICES³ database (<http://ecosystemdata.ices.dk/http://www.ices.dk/marine-data/data-portals/Pages/ocean.aspx>). As spin up we let the uncoupled model run 15 years using GEM concentration and deposition fields from CMAQ. For this we used the CMAQ runs described above, which were performed for every fifth year and used interpolated data for the years in between.

Finally, to determine the air-sea exchange and its impact on the regional transport patterns of mercury in Europe, we run MECOSMO-CMAQ in parallel for two selected years 2000 and 2005. We chose these years after evaluating the availability of observations on elemental mercury in the surface ocean, air-sea exchange, and atmospheric mercury concentrations.

3. Model evaluation

For the evaluation of the modelled air-sea exchange and its impact, measurements of GEM in the atmosphere and dissolved gaseous mercury (DGM) (which is used synonymous to the model species dissolved elemental mercury DEM) in the surface ocean are needed. Additionally, data to estimate the air-sea flux are needed. These include shipborne GEM measurements as well as observations of water temperature and wind speed. Especially the combination of mercury measurements in atmosphere and ocean is not commonly found for the North- and Baltic Sea.

In the atmosphere we use data from five EMEP stations: DE02 (Waldhof, Germany), DE07 (Neuglobsow, Germany), DE09 (Zingst, Germany), SE14 (Raö, Sweden), FI36 (Pallas, Finland) (Fig. 2a). Raö is located directly at the Swedish coast at the outermost part of the Baltic Sea, the Kattegat. Zingst is located at the German coast of the Arkona Sea. Pallas is a remote station located inland in the North of Finland and should not be influenced by mercury from the Baltic Sea. Waldhof and Neuglobsow are both located 100 to 200 km inland, south of the Baltic Sea and are used to evaluate the impact of the air-sea exchange on the regional transport of mercury.

In addition shipborne observations from seven cruises in the western and central Baltic Sea are used for the model evaluation. This includes two cruises in the central Baltic Sea in 1997 and 1998 where both marine and atmospheric mercury concentrations were measured (Wängberg et al., 2001), one cruise in 2000 when total mercury concentrations near the German coast were observed (Wurl et al., 2001), and four cruises in 2006 to evaluate the seasonal variability of the air-sea exchange (Kuss and Schneider, 2007). Moreover, observations at Swedish rivers and coastline from Garfeldt et al., (2001) are used to evaluate the impact of river inflow. Finally, we use DGM observations from three cruises in the North Sea (Coquery and Cossa, 1992; Coquery and Cossa, 1995,) and data from a platform in the German Bight (Baeyens and Leermakers, 1998). The sample locations are given in Figure 2b for those cruises where they were reported. For some cruises only approximate sampling locations could be obtained.

3.1 Dissolved elemental mercury

Only a small fraction of mercury in the ocean exists as elemental Hg⁰. In order to model the air-sea exchange of mercury the model needs to be capable to reproduce dissolved elemental mercury (DEM) concentrations in the surface water.

Comparison to 20 measurements in July 1997 and March 1998 show that 15 out of 20 values are within a factor of 2 of the observations (Fig. 3) with a mean concentration of 17.9 ng/m³ (observation) and 22.7 ng/m³ (model). The normalized mean bias (NMB) is 0.27 with a mean normalized bias (MNB) of 0.21 and a mean normalized error (MNE) of 0.53. The formulas used to calculate these statistics are given in Appendix A. These results seem remarkable, given that atmospheric models typically reproduce GEM (or TGM) concentrations within an accuracy of 10% (Bullock et al. 2008). Four samples can be

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3 identified for which the model strongly overestimates DEM concentrations. Samples 9, 10, and 11 were taken on the 12th
4 and 13th of July 1997 and are all inside the same grid cell, located near at the German coast. Here, the modeled DEM
5 concentrations exhibit a strong inter-daily variability during summer. Two days earlier modeled DEM concentration at this
6 point is 26 ng/l, two days later it is at 102 ng/l. This shows, that the model is able to produce comparable DEM
7 concentrations also at this location.

8
9 The data from Wängberg et al. (2001) was taken mainly in the Arkona and Bornhom Sea. Because of the large influx from
10 rivers, the model gives much higher mercury concentrations in the Belt Sea, as compared to other regions of the Baltic Sea.
11 On a cruise by Wurl et al. (2001) in this region during winter 2000, very high total mercury concentrations in the range of
12 200 to 1870 ng/m³ were observed. The model gives total mercury concentrations between 90 ng/m³ and 5000 ng/m³ for this
13 region. Concerning DEM, modelled values are in the range of 6 ng/m³ to 1200 ng/m³ with the maximum concentrations in
14 river inflow grid cells directly at the coast. This is in line with the findings of Garfeldt et al. (2001) who report more than 10
15 times higher concentrations in rivers at the Swedish coast compared to seawater. Zhijia et al. (2011) published a global
16 review on DEM concentrations at coastal sites. They report DEM concentrations at coastal sites between 6 ng/m³ and 176
17 ng/m³, and for the Baltic Sea between 17 and 100 ng/m³. Given these observations, we think that the very high modeled
18 concentration at the German coast are in a realistic order of magnitude. However, the local and temporal modelled
19 variability in DEM concentrations might be subject to uncertainty due to high uncertainty in spatial and temporal variations
20 of river loads.

21 The DEM concentrations dependent (among others) on temperature, solar radiation, biological activity, and atmospheric
22 GEM concentrations (Kuss et al., 2015). Therefore, they are subject to strong spatial and temporal variability. For further
23 model evaluation we used seasonal average DGM concentrations for different regions of the Baltic Sea measured in a series
24 of ship cruises in 2006 (Kuss and Schneider, 2007). Figure 4 depicts the seasonal variability of surface water DEM. The
25 observed values are based on measurements along the ship track and the model value is an average for the whole region.
26 Modeled values are based on three monthly averages for 2006, while the observations are based on four cruises in February,
27 April, July, and November 2006. The observations indicate increased DEM concentrations during spring and summer with
28 the peaks becoming more pronounced from west to east (from west to east: Belt, Arkona, Bornholm, Gotland Sea, Bothnian
29 Sea). For all regions, the model is able to reproduce this general seasonal cycle. In the Arkona Sea the model overestimates
30 the summer peak by 20% and underestimates the winter minimum by 20%. In the Bornholm Sea, the model leads to higher
31 values during winter than the observations. For the Bothnian Sea, where no observations are available, the model gives a
32 similar seasonal cycle as for the Gotland Sea but with an even more pronounced summer peak.

33 For the North Sea, there are less observations available compared to the Baltic Sea. In May 1996, Baeyens and Leermakers
34 (1998) observed DGM concentrations of 12.0 ng/m³ at a platform in the German Bight. In the corresponding grid cell
35 modelled average concentrations for May are 10.2 ng/m³. For the Schelde Estuarie, they report DGM concentrations of 42-
36 50 ng/m³ for winter and 80-108ng/m³ for summer. The model gives 35-78 ng/m³ for winter and 93-247 ng/m³ for summer
37 1996. Coquery and Cossa (1992; 1995) published DEM concentrations for 18 samples taken all over the North Sea in July
38 1991. Unfortunately, the MECOSMO runs do not include this year. However, these observations were compared to model
39 data from 1996. For July 1991 Coquery and Cossa (1995) found DGM concentrations at the Schelde estuarie in the range of
40 36-90 ng/m³. This is comparable to findings from Baeyens and Leermakers (1998) for the year 1996. Also at other estuaries
41 the model compares well with observations: Seine (obs: 50ng/m³, model: 34 ng/m³), Thames (obs: 68 ng/m³ model:
42 21ng/m³), Humber: (obs: 50 ng/m³ model: 41ng/m³), Ems (obs: 52 ng/m³ model: 47 ng/m³), Elbe: (obs: 54 ng/m³ model: 40
43 ng/m³), and three samples taken at the Dutch coast starting south of the Schelde northwards: (obs: 36 ng/m³ model: 14
44 ng/m³, obs: 76 ng/m³ model: 90 ng/m³, obs: 38 ng/m³ model: 46 ng/m³) (see Fig. 2B for sampling locations). At the Danish
45 North Sea coast (obs: 38 ng/m³) and in the Skaggerag (obs: 84 ng/m³) the model exhibits strong local DEM peaks whose
46 location differs from year to year. Here, the model gives DEM concentrations up to 50 ng/m³ (see Fig. 10 in Section 4.2).
47 Also in the northern, open North Sea high DGM concentrations were observed: Scottish coast (obs: 42 ng/m³) and
48 Norwegian coast (obs: 70 ng/m³). In the model, DEM concentration in this region vary between 10-40 ng/m³ during summer
49 and 20-80 ng/m³ in spring. Finally, Coquery and Cossa (1995) report DGM concentrations in the central Baltic to be lower
50 than the detection limit of their method (20ng/m³). For this region the model gives DEM concentrations between 5 and
51 10ng/m³. This is also in line with the observations by Baeyens and Leermakers (1998) with 12 ng/m³ in the German Bight.
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54 3.2 Air-Sea exchange

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56 The evaluation of air-sea fluxes calculated with MECOSMO-CMAQ is difficult because there are no direct measurements
57 available. Observational based fluxes are calculated based on measurements of DGM and TGM (Wängberg et al., 2001;
58 Kuss & Schneider; 2007). Based on the observed wind speed and water temperature, different parametrizations for the
59 Henry's Law constant, the diffusivity of gaseous mercury in water, and the transfer velocity between the compartments are
60 used to calculate an effective Hg flux (see Section 2.2). Wängberg et al. (2001) calculated fluxes using a parametrization
61 based on Wannikhof (1992) and Kuss and Schneider (2007) a parameterization based on Weiss et al. (2007). Both exhibit a
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3 stronger wind dependency than the parametrization used for this study. Since Wängberg et al. (2001) published all data
4 used to calculate their air-sea fluxes, we could recalculate the fluxes based on their data, but using the parameterization
5 according to the formulation used for the model simulations (see Section 2.2). This recalculation increased the average air-
6 sea flux reported by Wängberg from 25 ng/m² to 34 ng/m² (N=20) as compared to a modeled flux of 42 ng/m². Generally,
7 the recalculated fluxes are in better agreement with modeled values. The NMB was reduced from 0.68 to 0.25, the MNB
8 from 1.7 to 1.0, and the MNE from 2.9 to 1.5 (Fig. 5). The formulas used to calculate these statistics are given in Appendix
9 A. A comparison of the fluxes published by Wängberg et al. (2001) with those based on the same observations and the
10 parametrization given in Section 2.2 are NMB=0.35, MNB=0.93, MNE=1.2, illustrating how strongly the calculated air-sea
11 flux depends on the chosen parametrization. The differences in flux estimation are mainly influenced by different
12 parametrizations of the wind speed dependency of the transfer velocity. The difference between model and observation is in
13 the same range as the differences between observational based estimates using different flux-parameterisations

14 The air-sea fluxes calculated by Kuss and Schneider could not be recalculated because data on wind speed, temperature, and
15 atmospheric GEM concentrations used to calculate these fluxes are not available to us. Given the findings from the
16 recalculation of the air-sea fluxes published by Wängberg et al. (2001) we can already assume a uncertainty of a factor of 2
17 for the individual values. Figure 6 depicts modelled daily average air-sea fluxes for different regions of the Baltic Sea. In
18 addition, the 66% and 90% quantile ranges are given to indicate the regional variability. The Belt Sea exhibits a large
19 variability with 66% of the mercury fluxes are between 100 and 1000 ng/m². This can be explained by the large riverine
20 inflow of mercury in this region. Generally, the model gives a strong decreasing gradient with increasing distance to the
21 coast. For the Belt Sea observed fluxes are mostly on the lower end of the 66% quantile range with the exception of mid
22 November, when fluxes are much lower than during the rest of the season. Here, the observations are similar to the model
23 mean flux. The Arkona Sea has similar, albeit less pronounced, features as the Belt Sea. However, in this region
24 observations during winter, spring, and summer are close to modelled mean fluxes. In November the model calculates a
25 peak, leading to the highest fluxes of the whole year with values much higher than the observations. This peak is mainly
26 driven by strong winds calculated by COSMO-CLM. In the Bornholm Sea, the model gives a much smaller variability. Here
27 model and observation are in good agreement. Especially, the near zero flux observed in February coincides with the time
28 when modelled fluxes change from a net flow into the ocean to a net flow into the atmosphere. This holds also true for
29 observations made during February in the western and eastern Gotland Sea. In the western Gotland Sea the high fluxes
30 observed during July are inside the 90% quantile range, while in the eastern Gotland Sea the summer peak is in the range of
31 the maximum fluxes calculated by the model for this region.
32

3.1 Atmospheric mercury concentrations

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35 In Table 2 the normalized mean bias (NMB) of modelled gaseous elemental mercury (GEM) is given for the years 2000 and
36 2005 for the five EMEP stations (see Fig.2) as calculated by CMAQ and ECOSMO-CMAQ. It can be seen, that the CMAQ
37 run tends to underestimate GEM concentrations. On average, the model bias is around -10%. This value is dominated by a
38 strong underestimation of GEM at Waldhof (-0.29). This is a very uncommon finding, as the model is usually able to
39 reproduce GEM concentrations at Waldhof within an error of less than 10% (Bieser et al., 2014). The evaluation is based on
40 daily observations with a sample size of: Zingst N=365, Raö N=83, Pallas N=365, Neuglobsow N=8784, Waldhof
41 N=39528.
42

43 The best agreement between model and observation is found for FI36 which is not deemed to be influenced by air-sea
44 exchange due to it's inland location north of the Baltic Sea. For Raö, model and observations are in even better agreement
45 for 1995 (NMB=-0.02) and 2000 (NMB=0.02). However, in 2005 the model underestimates the GEM concentrations by
46 16%. This is due to an episode with polluted air masses not captured by CMAQ. At Zingst, the model constantly
47 underestimates GEM concentrations by about 10% in each year.
48

49 When running CMAQ using the air-sea fluxes calculated by MECOSMO and comparing to the default CMAQ simulation
50 we see no change in concentrations at Pallas and only a small increase of GEM concentrations of 2% at Raö. However, in
51 Zingst GEM concentrations increase by about 10% and the model is in very good agreement with observations (Table 2).
52 Moreover, the model is now able to reproduce several peaks observed at Zinst (Fig. 7). At Raö only a small number of GEM
53 peaks is observed, which might be rather due to the lower resolution of the observations as because of their absence. At
54 Waldhof (+5%) and Neuglobsow (+2.5%), the air-sea exchange has a smaller, albeit positive, effect on modeled GEM
55 concentrations. Also at these stations the implementation of emissions from the Baltic Sea leads to a better reproduction of
56 daily peaks observed at these stations. A comparison of CMAQ-MECOSMO results for 2000 and 2005 show similar effects
57 on atmospheric GEM concentrations in both years on average decreasing the model bias by 33%.
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4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Air-sea exchange in the Baltic Sea

Figure 8 depicts seasonally averaged DEM concentrations in the model surface layer. On average, the highest concentrations occur in summer and autumn with the largest DEM peaks found during spring. These peaks are directly linked to biological activity leading to increased reduction of oxidized mercury (Fig. 1). The lowest DEM concentrations are found in winter. This is due to the low biological activity during winter and due to winter mixing, which increases the surface mixed layer depth from roughly 10m to 20m in summer to around 100m in winter (e.g. Janssen et al., 1999). In shallow waters the amount of particulate matter is higher in winter compared to offshore waters because of near coastal resuspension induced by high wind speeds in winter. This leads to a larger fraction of mercury bound to particles, which is not available for reduction. Moreover convective winter mixing has no substantial effect near the coast, because of lower water depths.

The highest DEM concentrations are found near the German coast in the Belt and Arkona Sea and the Polish coast near Danzig. To a large extent this can be attributed to the fact that the prescribed riverine mercury loads can be up to 200 ng/l in these areas. The model indicates that there is an annual minimum in the north-eastern Gotland Basin and the Bothnian Sea. Here, average DEM concentrations as low as 2 ng/m³ are calculated by the model. However, the observations by Kuss et al. (2006) indicate that the model underestimates peak concentrations in the Gotland Sea during summer time. In the Bothnian Bay the fraction of DEM compared to the total mercury concentration is higher than in the rest of the Baltic Sea, because of the higher reduction potential caused by the very low salinity (0-2 PSU at the northern most part of the Baltic Sea).

The variability of the air-sea exchange (Fig. 6 and 9) is mainly determined by the variability of DEM surface concentrations. GEM concentrations in the atmosphere vary between between 1.2 and 2.0 ng/m³. This equals a variability of 50% around the atmospheric average of 1.5ng/m³. In comparison, DEM shows a much larger variability on the seasonal scale (Fig. 8). However, the higher GEM concentrations in winter, which are caused by higher emissions and a lower planetary boundary layer, intensify the seasonal cycle of the air-sea exchange dominated by DEM. At typical winter temperatures DEM concentrations above 8 ng/m³ are needed for a Hg flux into the atmosphere. Because of the dependency on the Henry's Law constant and the diffusivity of gaseous mercury in the water, during summer only around 6 ng/m³ are needed for an effective Hg flux into the atmosphere. These values are estimated based on average values for atmospheric GEM concentrations, temperature, and the Henry's Law constant (Eq. 4-1) for winter and summer.

Table 3 gives seasonal fluxes averaged over a 14 year period from 1994 to 2007. In the model, the central Baltic is a sink for mercury during winter and in the northern part of the Gotland and in the Bothnian Sea even during spring and autumn. The fluxes into the atmosphere are larger in the coastal regions following the DEM concentration gradients depicted in Figure 8. We calculated the total mercury flux from the Baltic Sea, ignoring 14 river inflow grid cells which have extremely high DEM concentrations in the model. Albeit the small area, in the model these grid cells have an impact on the total mercury evasion from the Baltic Sea. It would be of high interest to see whether observations can verify these patterns produced by the model. Observations at the Swedish coast by Garfeldt et al. (2001) indicate that DGM concentrations in rivers are more than 10 times higher than in the open ocean. In the model, river inflow grid cells have up to 25 times higher concentrations compared to the open ocean grid cells.

The calculated average annual mercury evasion from the entire Baltic Sea is 7450±500 kg/a (winter 1160±180 kg/a, spring 1680±310 kg/a, summer 2275±210 kg/a, autumn 2329±195 kg/a). The inter-annual variability is 20% (6500 kg/a to 8100 kg/a). The variability is mainly driven by the air-sea exchange in the Belt Sea and the Arkona Sea which are responsible for 67% of the total mercury evasion in the Baltic Sea (Table 4). The Bays of Bothnia, Finland, and Riga contribute 25% to the total. The North Gotland Sea is the only region with an annual net influx into the ocean. The modelled average mercury flux for different regions of the Baltic Sea is given in Table 4. Kuss et al. (2007) estimated the annual mercury evasion from the central Baltic (235000 km²) for 2006 to be in the range of 2700 kg/a – 5900 kg/a. For this region, which excludes the Gulfs of Bothnia, Finland, and Riga the model calculates a flux of 5470 kg/a in 2006.

4.2 Air-sea exchange in the North Sea

In the North Sea the model predicts high DEM surface concentrations at the Dutch and German coast. These are caused by the inflow of polluted water from the large rivers along the coast. The high concentrations are transported northwards along the European coast line. (Fig. 10) For the same reasons as in the Baltic Sea DEM concentrations are lowest during winter. The highest concentrations are found during spring and summer. The northern North Sea exhibits the strongest seasonal variability with the lowest concentrations during winter and the highest concentrations during summer. The high concentrations during summer in the north western North Sea are caused by increased reduction of dissolved oxidized mercury because of the inflow of phytoplankton rich water from the Atlantic. Moreover, the model estimates large DEM

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3 peaks during spring and summer in the north western North Sea and the Skaggerag which coincide with high total mercury
4 concentrations in this area. Moreover, the model estimates a pronounced minimum in DEM concentrations during autumn in
5 the region of the Norwegian trench and in the central North Sea north of the Dogger Bank extending towards the British
6 coast.

7 Like the Baltic Sea, the North Sea is a net emitter of mercury with 2850 ± 460 kg/a (winter -360 ± 90 , spring 930 ± 320 ,
8 summer 1210 ± 120 , autumn 1070 ± 145) (Table 5). On average, the North Sea emits only about a third of the mercury emitted
9 by the Baltic Sea. However, with 55% the relative inter-annual variability is much larger than in the Baltic Sea. The
10 seasonal cycle is similar to the Baltic, with the highest emissions during summer and autumn. During winter the North Sea
11 is a sink for atmospheric mercury. Figure 11 depicts seasonal average mercury flux between the North Sea and the
12 atmosphere. It can be seen, that the maximum air-sea flux into the ocean occurs during winter in the northern North Sea.
13 Generally, the air-sea exchange follows the DEM concentrations as depicted in Figure 10.
14

15 16 **4.3 Atmospheric transport**

17 A comparison to data from EMEP stations indicates that the air-sea flux influences GEM concentrations on a regional scale
18 during spring, summer, and autumn. Figure 12 depicts difference plots between CMAQ and CMAQ-MECOSMO runs.,
19 indicating the amount of GEM in the atmosphere originating from the North- and Baltic Sea. On average GEM
20 concentrations are increased by between 1% (winter) and 5% (summer) in the Baltic Sea region through coupling to the
21 ocean model. However, for individual episodes GEM concentrations can increase up to 25% in areas more than 1000km
22 away. In regions with strong riverine mercury inflow GEM concentrations are increased significantly (e.g. 10% at Zingst on
23 annual average). Because around 50% of the mercury deposition over land is due to dry deposition of GEM, this will also
24 influence the total mercury deposition over land. However, no observations are available to validate the impact of the
25 emissions from the Baltic Sea on mercury dry deposition.
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28 29 **5. Conclusions**

30 In this study, we coupled a regional chemistry transport model for the atmosphere (CMAQ) to a newly developed eulerian
31 chemistry transport model for the regional ocean (MECOSMO) to investigate the air-sea exchange of mercury in the North-
32 and Baltic Sea. Modeled concentrations of elemental mercury in both compartments proved to be in good agreement with
33 observations. The calculated air-sea exchange in the Baltic Sea region was verified through comparisons to observation
34 based estimates calculated from shipborne observations. The model was able to reproduce observed surface water
35 concentrations of dissolved elemental mercury and air-sea exchange in the North- and Baltic Sea. Also the seasonal
36 variability of modelled values compared reasonably with observations in the Baltic Sea. Previous regional estimates of
37 annual mercury evasions could be confirmed and the model further allowed to provide first estimates for annual mercury
38 evasions and their variability from both seas. The modeled average annual mercury evasion into the atmosphere for the time
39 from 1994 to 2008 is in the range of 6500 kg/a to 8100 kg/a for the Baltic Sea and 2400 to 3950 kg/a for the North Sea.
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41 The model indicates that there is a strong gradient in the air-sea flux from highly polluted coastal regions in the Belt and
42 Arkona Sea, which dominate the total mercury evasion from the Baltic Sea (67% of the total). The second largest source
43 areas are the Bays of Riga (11%), Finland (8%), and Bothnia (6%). Moreover, the model predicts very low concentrations of
44 dissolved elemental mercury in the Gotland Sea and the Bothnian Sea. In the model, these regions are sinks for atmospheric
45 mercury during winter and exhibit a near zero net mercury flux on annual average. Also observations indicate this reversal
46 of the flux during winter in the Bornholm and Gotland Seas (Kuss et al., 2007). The North Gotland Sea is the only region
47 where the model predicts a net flux into the ocean on annual average.

48 Investigating the seasonal cycle of mercury evasion from the Baltic, the model indicates a minimum during winter time,
49 which is due to lower dissolved elemental mercury (DEM) concentrations in the ocean and higher gaseous elemental
50 mercury concentrations (GEM) in the atmosphere. The GEM concentrations are increased because of higher emissions from
51 coal fired power plants and a lower planetary boundary layer. Because of the much smaller gradient during winter, the high
52 wind speeds in this season have no significant effect of the air-sea exchange. During spring and summer the air-sea
53 exchange is mainly driven by high DEM concentrations in the ocean which are caused by the high biological activity and
54 the connected bio-reduction of dissolved oxidized mercury. During autumn higher wind speeds compensate for the lower
55 elemental mercury gradient between ocean and atmosphere and lead to a net mercury evasion similar to spring and summer
56 for the whole Baltic Sea. The seasonal cycle in the North Sea is similar to the Baltics Sea. During winter the North Sea is, on
57 average, a sink for atmospheric mercury with -360 ± 90 kg/a.
58

59 A comparison of average DEM concentrations and air-sea fluxes for the Bornholm and Gotland Sea indicate that the model
60 could be missing strong local DEM peaks during summer. It is expected, that the observed peaks are linked to biological
61 activity. Indeed, the model does exhibit DEM peaks, and peaks in air-sea flux, correlated to primary production. It cannot be
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3 verified whether the observations coincide with such a spatially and locally temporal peak in primary production or whether
4 the model generally underestimates DEM concentrations in this region. Additional observations would be necessary and
5 more detailed model sensitivity studies in the future could increase the insight into the marine cycling of DEM and help to
6 resolve this question.

7 Finally, we investigated the impact of mercury emissions from the North- and Baltic Sea on atmospheric transport of GEM.
8 A comparison of downwind EMEP stations showed, that the model performance improves when including these emissions.
9 Directly at the German coast, GEM concentrations are increased by more than 10% on annual average. Moreover, GEM
10 peaks with a duration of up to a few days could be attributed to air-sea exchange from the Baltic. In a vicinity of 100 km to
11 200km the annual effect is reduced to 2% to 5%. However, at individual days, depending on atmospheric conditions, GEM
12 evasion from the Baltic Sea can still have large impacts even on a regional scale.
13

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24
25

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32 Appendix A

33 P_i = Predicted value from Model

34 O_i = Observed value

35 N = sample size

36 Mean

$$\bar{O} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N O_i \quad \bar{P} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N P_i \quad (\text{A1})$$

37 Mean Normalized Bias (NMB)

$$MNB = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{P_i - O_i}{O_i} \right) \quad (\text{A2})$$

38 Mean Normalized Error (MNE)

$$MNE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{|P_i - O_i|}{O_i} \right) \quad (\text{A3})$$

39 Normalized Mean Error (NME)

$$NME = \frac{|\bar{P} - \bar{O}|}{\bar{O}} \quad (\text{A4})$$

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66 Figures

67 *Figure 1: Mercury species and reactions implemented in MECOSMO*

68 *Figure 2: a) CMAQ model domain and location of EMEP measurement stations. b) ECOSMO domain and sampling*
69 *locations from ship cruises. North Sea: red squares (Coquery and Cossa, 1992), yellow circles (Baeyens and Leermakers,*

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3 1997). Baltic Sea: yellow squares winter 1997, red circles summer 1998 (Wängberg et al., 2001).

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5 Figure 3: Comparison of observed DGM concentrations in the central Baltic to model DEM concentrations (Wängberg et al., 2001). Modelled values are daily averages while the observations are snapshots.

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7 Figure 4: Normalized dissolved elemental mercury concentrations in surface water. Comparison of observations from Kuss

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9 Figure 5: Comparison of air-sea fluxes calculated by Wängberg et al. (2001) (red) and ECOSMO-CMAQ (blue). The observations were taken in the Bornholm and Gotland Sea area. The dashed boxes depict recalculated fluxes based on observations by Wängberg and the parametrization described in Section 2.2.

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11 Figure 6: Seasonal variability of air-sea flux for different regions of the Baltic Sea based on observations by Kuss and Schneider (2007) (red boxes). Model values are the regional average (blue), the 66% quantile range (light-blue), and the 90% quantile range (light-pink).

12
13 Figure 7: Gaseous elemental mercury concentration at DE09 Zingst for the year 2000 (top) and 2005 (bottom). Statistics for this and other stations are given in Table 2.

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15 Figure 8: Seasonally averaged dissolved elemental mercury (DEM) concentration in model surface layer (5m depth) for 1998. From left to right: winter (Dec-Feb), spring (Mar-May), summer (Jun-Aug), autumn (Sep-Nov).

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17 Figure 9: Seasonally averaged daily air-sea flux for the Baltic Sea in 1998 (negative values indicate a flux into the atmosphere). From left to right: winter, spring, summer, autumn.

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19 Figure 10: Seasonal average DEM concentrations in the North Sea surface layer (5m layer depth) for 1996. From left to right: winter, spring, summer, autumn.

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21 Figure 11: Seasonally averaged mercury flux from the North Sea for 1996. From left to right: winter, spring, summer, autumn.

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23 Figure 12: Impact of air-sea coupling on atmospheric GEM concentration, seasonally averaged concentration increase due to air-sea exchange in the North- and Baltic Sea for the year 2000. From left to right: winter, spring, summer, autumn.

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Reaction	Rate	Unit
Dark oxidation	1.0E-7	s ⁻¹
Photo oxidation	6.6E-6	ng ² W ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
Photo reduction	1.7E-6	ng ² W ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
Bio reduction	4.5E-6	l mg ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
Methylation	1.0E-8	s ⁻¹
Dark demethylation	1.0E-8	s ⁻¹
Photo demethylation	1.0E-9	ng ² W ⁻¹ s ⁻¹

Table 1: Reaction rates for aquatic mercury reactions

Station	2000		2005	
	CMAQ	CMAQ-MECOSMO	CMAQ	CMAQ-MECOSMO
DE09, Zingst	-0.11	0.02	-0.10	-0.03
SE14, Raö	0.02	0.03	-0.16	-0.14
FI36, Pallas	-0.06	-0.06	-0.03	-0.02
DE02 Waldhof	-	-	-0.29	-0.25
DE07 Neuglobsow	-	-	-0.13	-0.12

Table 2: Normalized Mean Bias for EMEP station in the Baltic region with (right) and without (left) air-sea exchange of mercury.

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Year	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007
Hg flux [kg/a]	7766	8005	6837	7164	8106	7700	7518	7159	7638	6529	7651	7464	6870	7959

Table 3: Annual total mercury evasion for the entire Baltic Sea.

Region	Winter [ng/m ² day]	Spring [ng/m ² day]	Summer [ng/m ² day]	Autumn [ng/m ² day]	Annual [ng/m ² day]	Annual [kg/a]
Belt Sea	484	622	524	481	449	2431 (33%)
Arkona Sea	240	302	225	248	210	2564 (34%)
Bornholm Sea	39	59	72	80	54	312
West Gotland Sea	-14	2	22	19	8	99
East Gotland Sea	-19	0	13	13	3	81
North Gotland Sea	-24	-8	6	12	-2	-15
Bothnian Sea	-16	-3	17	14	4	103
Bay of Bothnia	-2	4	75	66	34	445 (6%)
Bay of Finland	26	19	79	84	46	628 (8%)
Bay of Riga	202	102	188	237	156	807 (11%)
Baltic Sea	36	52	70	72	57	7456

Table 4: Average modelled seasonal air-Sea flux of mercury [ng/m² day] for different Baltic Sea regions. Negative values are fluxes from the atmosphere into the ocean. Archipelago and Aland Sea are included in the Bothnian Sea. The Gdansk Basin is included in the East Gotland Sea.

Year	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007
Hg flux [kg/a]	3943	3434	3371	2772	2839	2637	2662	2393	2487	2411	2624	2737	2408	3142

Table 5: Annual total mercury evasion for the entire North Sea.

A generalized approach to model bioaccumulation of Methylmercury in fish and Macrobenthos

Corinna Schrum, Sebastian Mentze, Johannes Bieser, Ute Daewel

1. Introduction

The mercury burden in the ocean has increased by a factor of 5 since pre-industrial times (Amos et al., 2013) and further increase is expected, due to still increasing fossil fuel combustion and small-scale artisanal gold mining in Asia (UNEP/AMAP, 2012, UNEP, 2013a). Persistent environmental pollutants and heavy metals, that occur in low concentrations in the environment can however bioaccumulate in seafood and biomagnification might occur. Bioaccumulation of mercury is a significant and much studied problem, as high levels of methylmercury (MeHg) in seafood have detrimental or even fatal effects on humans (Example: Björnberg et al. 2005; Yorifuji et al. 2011). Mercury levels increased substantially in some Arctic and Nordatlantic species during the last decades and concentrations are getting alarmingly high as a result of anthropogenic activities (Lamborg et al., 2014). Mercury pollution is therefore getting increasingly important for the health of the marine ecosystem and assessment of mercury contamination pathways are of vital interest.

The majority of mercury is released as inorganic mercury, and the more toxic organic species are produced under biogeochemical cycling. Of most concern is MeHg since it is a potent neurotoxin, which bioaccumulates in organisms and low degradation and excretion rates lead to biomagnification (Chen et al., 2012). The level of MeHg is controlled by methylation of inorganic mercury and demethylation of MeHg (Li & Cai, 2013). Methylation takes place both in sediments and the water column, the open ocean and the Arctic are key regions for the latter. The factors controlling MeHg bioavailability and uptake from water to plankton are critical but have been poorly investigated (Douglas et al., 2012) and observations resolving the different species and in relation to organic ligands are rare. The relative contribution of periphyton or water methylation vs sediment methylation remains still uncertain due to lacking observational evidence and lacking modelling capacity. Hence, quantitative assessments of production and diffusion rates and hypotheses about regional and climate induced variations in methylation and MeHg remain so far speculative (Stern et al., 2012).

Current atmospheric chemistry models are able to reproduce and predict concentrations of elemental mercury on a shorter timescale (e.g. Hynes et al., 2009) but little has so far been done to model mercury cycling in the ocean or in the coupled system. State of the art modelling approaches either neglect mercury chemistry in the water column (e.g. Green et al., 2012) or consider only highly simplified ocean representations (e.g. Fisher et al., 2013; Soerensen et al., 2011). By now, the only fully three-dimensional atmosphere-ocean model that features complete mercury chemistry, including methylation and demethylation processes and considers exchange of mercury between atmosphere, ocean, marine biosphere and sediments, is the newly developed MECOSMO-CMAQ, which is currently applied to the North and Baltic Sea (Schrum & Bieser, 2013; Bieser and Schrum, in review).

Predicting trophic transfer of mercury and contamination of marine organisms is even more complex, it depends on the local relative contribution of mercury species and in particular on the level of MeHg, the uptake and feeding behaviour of different organisms, migration of species and the position of the species in the food web (Douglas et al., 2012; Julshamn 2013a&b). Hydrodynamic processes organise species spatially with aggregation along fronts, divergences or upwelling zones, this effect both, the uptake of mercury by prey and prey consumption (see review by Douglas et al, 2012). Modelling these processes explicitly and considering them in seafood safety models such as those developed by the National Institute of Nutrition and Seafood Research (NIFES) is currently limited by lacking 3-d

ocean modelling approaches and the challenges in spatially explicit modelling of higher trophics. However, the first model concepts have been developed and different approaches have been published for different species (e.g. Radtke et al., 2013; Utne et al., 2012). A novel functional group fish model ECOMSO-E2E was developed in the frame of the EU-FP7 project SEAMAN (<http://www.org.uib.no/seaman/>; Daewel and Schrum, 2016; manuscript for submission) and the linking of such models with 3-d mercury models in the ocean forms a first step in spatially resolved sea-food safety predictions.

The aim of this study was to link these two model approaches, the ECOSMO-E2E fish model and the MECOSMO-CMAQ environmental mercury model to study bioaccumulation and biomagnification pathways in fish and to present an approach to combine the ecosystem and mercury modules.

2. Methods

Detailed description of the mercury model MECOSMO-CMAQ was presented by Bieser and Schrum (in review) and the model was validated against atmospheric and oceanic observations of mercury and found to well reproduce observed structures in environmental mercury distributions. It was found the model in particular increased the performance to model the spatial and temporal variations in atmospheric concentrations by considering the oceanic pool and chemical transformation processes in the ocean (Bieser and Schrum, in review).

The ECOSMO-E2E model, which extended the lower trophic level concept of the ECOSMO model (Schrum et al., 2006; Daewel and Schrum, 2013) by a macrobenthos and a fish functional group was presented by Daewel and Schrum (2016). It could be shown, that the model replicated realistic structures of fish production and biomass pattern. Seasonal and regional pattern of macrobenthos and fish dynamics were in accordance to present understanding and modelled biomass levels were close to independent earlier observational estimates (Daewel & Schrum, 2016).

The 4-D ECOSMO-E2E model fields of biomass and production (biomass consumed * assimilation efficiency per prey group) for the year 2008 were used and from the MECOSMO-CMAQ mercury model, the methylmercury concentrations separated into the concentrations in organic matter (detritus), phytoplankton, zooplankton and sediments were used. The following table gives an overview of the fields used to calculate the bioaccumulation in macrobenthos and fish:

Mercury module			
Variable	Abbreviation	Dimensions	Units
Methylmercury concentration in particulate organic matter (detritus)	MeHg_D	x,y,z,t	ngMeHg/l
Methylmercury concentration in Phytoplankton	MeHg_P	x,y,z,t	ngMeHg/l
Methylmercury concentration in Zooplankton	MeHg_Z	x,y,z,t	ngMeHg/l
Methylmercury concentration in organic sediments	MeHg_S	x,y,t	ngMeHg/m ²
Concentration of particulate organic matter, detritus	D	x,y,z,t	mg C/l

Concentration of Phytoplankton	P	x,y,z,t	mg C/l
Concentration of Zooplankton	Z	x,y,z,t	mg C/l
Organic sediments	biomass_sed	x,y,t	mg C/m ²

Macrobenthos and fish module			
Variable	Abbreviation	Dimensions	Units
Concentration of fish carbon biomass	F	x,y,z,t	mg C/m ³
Concentration of macrobenthos carbon biomass	MB	x,y,z,t	mg C/m ³
Macro benthos production on sediment	MBprod_S	x,y,z,t	mg C/m ³
Macro benthos benthos production on/assimilation of detritus	MBprod_D	x,y,z,t	mg C/m ³
Macro benthos benthos production on/assimilation of Zooplankton	MBprod_Z	x,y,z,t	mg C/m ³
Macro benthos benthos production on /assimilation of Phytoplankton	MBprod_P	x,y,z,t	mg C/m ³
Fish benthos production on/assimilation of small zooplankton	Fprod_Zs	x,y,z,t	mg C/m ³
Fish benthos production on /assimilation of large zooplankton	Fprod_Zl	x,y,z,t	mg C/m ³
Fish benthos production on/assimilation of detritus	Fprod_D	x,y,z,t	mg C/m ³
Fish benthos production on /assimilation of macrobenthos	Fprod_MB	x,y,z,t	mg C/m ³

The bioaccumulation was modelled by propagating the concentration of methylmercury throughout the food chain, as depicted in figure 1.

Figure 1: Food chain used to propagate methylmercury

For the initial prey items phytoplankton, zooplankton, sediment and detritus, the ratio of mercury per carbon (C) biomass was calculated by dividing the MeHg and biomass concentrations, for example:

$$MeHg_Z / Z(x, y, z, t) [ng\ mg^{-1}] = \frac{MeHg_Z(x, y, z, t)}{Z(x, y, z, t)}$$

Then, for the macrobenthos and fish group, the amount of assimilated MeHg was calculated by multiplying the concentration of assimilated C biomass with the ratio of MeHg per C biomass.

$$MeHg_{ass_Z}(x, y, z, t) [ng\ m^{-3}] = \frac{MeHg_Z(x, y, z, t)}{Z(x, y, z, t)} MBprod_Z(x, y, z, t)$$

For the fish group, the total assimilated MEHG was calculated by adding the assimilated MeHg from the different prey items:

$$MeHg_{ass}(x, y, z, t) [ng\ m^{-3}] = MeHg_{ass_Z}(x, y, z, t) + MeHg_{ass_D}(x, y, z, t) + MeHg_{ass_MB}(x, y, z, t)$$

The bioaccumulation of mercury in fish/year was then calculated for each location (latitude-longitude rectangle) under the assumption that all during the year assimilated MeHg will bioaccumulate. For each location, the amount of MeHg was integrated over the water column and over the year 2008. The ratio of MeHg/F mg MeHg/ kg C was then calculated by dividing the integrated MeHg by the depth integrated fish biomass at the end of 2008.

$$MeHg_F(x, y) \left[\frac{mg\ MeHg}{kg\ C\ fish\ a} \right] = \frac{\int_{bottom}^{surface} \int_0^{365} MeHg_{ass}(x, y, z, t) Vol(x, y, z) dt dz}{\int_{bottom}^{surface} F(x, y, z) Vol(x, y, z) dz}$$

3. Results

The amount of carbon assimilated by fish from each of the 4 prey items is displayed in figure 2. Significant amounts of biomass are assimilated by feeding on the macrobenthos and large zooplankton groups. These groups were also the 2 groups with the highest concentration of MeHg per carbon biomass, which is displayed for all prey items in Figure 3.

Figure 2: Depth averaged and time integrated fish production from each of the 4 prey items large and small zooplankton, detritus and macrobenthos

Figure 3: Annual mean MeHg concentration in the different prey items

Figure 4 displays how much MeHg the fish group assimilates from each of the 4 prey items each year. Most MeHg is bioaccumulated from the large Zooplankton and macrobenthos group, followed by feeding on detritus and small zooplankton.

Figure 4: Ratio of bioaccumulated mg MEHG per kg fish for each of the 4 prey items, depth and time integrated

The macrobenthos itself accumulates most MeHg from the sediment. Figure 5 displays the average amount of MeHg which is assimilated by the macrobenthos group from each of the 4 prey items.

Figure 5: Ratio of mg accumulated mg MEHG per kg macrobenthos for each of the 4 prey items, depth and time averaged

The total amount of bioaccumulation of MeHg calculated by annually integrated assimilated MeHg through fish production is displayed in figure 6.

Figure 6: Ratio of total annually accumulated mg MEHG per kg C fish

4. Discussion

The spatial patterns in MeHg bioaccumulation (Figure 6) suggest that most MeHg is accumulated in the central North Sea and along the outflows of major river systems in the Baltic. This agrees with our expectations, since most mercury enters the Baltic and North Sea through river input, mainly from industrial sources. However, surprisingly little MeHg was accumulated in the Elbe river plume, which is likely due to the strong tidal mixing and frequent water mass exchange in the southern North Sea. The overall levels of bioaccumulations agree with observations by Frantsen et al. 2015 and Julshamn et al., 2004 found mercury concentrations between 0.006 to 0.4 mg Hg per kg wet-weight in herring (planktivorous species) in the Norwegian Sea and North Sea with mercury concentration increasing with fish age. Higher concentrations were found eg for cod (Julshamn et al., 2013 ab), which are higher in the food chain and at larger age feed primarily on fish. Although bioaccumulation within the phytoplankton, zooplankton and macrobenthos groups was not resolved here, the calculated bioaccumulation of mercury in fish provides reasonable values. Further development of the method is however necessary to provide more exact numbers compared to observations to account for a more detailed conversion of estimates derived in mg Hg/mg carbon to mg Hg/kg wet weight.

Over all, this attempt to include the bioaccumulation of pollutants into hydrodynamic and ecosystem models, shows that realistic values and patterns can be predicted. With further development and verification, these models can provide information on the spatial and temporal distribution of bioaccumulation to inform ecosystem and fisheries management.

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